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DELIVERABLE 4.8 – INTERACTION CONCEPTS (FINAL VERSION)

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Executive summary

This deliverable presents the results of task T4.4 *“Multimodal interaction concepts and resulting requirements for XR-Technology and UI”*. The goal of this task was to develop a general interaction model, wherein all the envisioned control and feedback functions relevant to each of the THEIA^{XR} use-cases can be described. Using this, we broke down the interaction scenarios developed in task T3.2 *“Scenario-based co-design of interaction concepts”* into component control and feedback tasks. For each of these component tasks, we specify how these functions are concretely implemented inside a set of immersive playable simulation demonstrators. Input from the co-design process as well as insights gleaned during the implementation process allowed iterative refinement of the simulated interaction with UI components, which will continue during the subsequent demonstration and testing process (Tasks T6.2 *“Testing and Demonstration”* and T6.3 *“Validation and Evaluation Analysis and Lesson Learning”*). The present document is the final version of the previously submitted D4.4 *“Interaction concepts”*, it summarizes the interaction model, the functional specification derived from the interaction scenarios from D3.2, as well as the functions implemented in the immersive playable demos for all three THEIA^{XR} use-cases.

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1 Introduction

Deliverable D4.8 builds upon deliverable D4.4 *“Interaction Concepts”* (submitted 27/03/2024) and aims to produce a general model of interactions, along with a set of immersive playable demonstrations showcasing novel control and feedback functions developed for each of the use-cases considered in THEIA^{XR}. This document begins by presenting the interaction model, followed by a function specification derived from the interaction scenarios provided by work package WP3 *“Transdisciplinary Co-Design”* (in particular through the work done in task T3.2 *“Scenario-based co-design of interaction concepts”*). Finally, it details the actual implementation of each of the designed functions as well as the simulation environments in which these function demonstrations are implemented.

The implementation of these simulated functions closely interacted with UI and hardware development taking place in work packages WP4 *“Cyber-Physical Human-Machine Interaction”* and WP5 *“Multimodal Information Presentation”*. Indeed, novel concepts for XR UI components led to the ideation of more precise interaction concepts, while attempts to implement these interaction concepts highlighted requirements and potential shortcomings of original XR UI component and interaction concepts. Since implementation of the simulated UI functions required interaction between several hardware components, and since it attempted to model real-world interactions with the vehicles as closely as was feasible, it also provides a foundation for integration work which is the focus of work-package WP6 *“Integration, Demonstration, Validation and Verification”*. As such, the created demonstrators can serve as a foundation for some of the testing work ongoing in work-package WP6.

As work on task T3.2 *“Scenario-based co-design of interaction concepts”* followed the same timeline as work on the present deliverable, the XR UI specification and implemented demonstrator functions are based on the state of the interaction scenarios as they stood as of February 2025. Some late-breaking inputs from the co-design process may therefore not entirely match the interaction demonstrator contents, but could form the basis for subsequent evolutions during the final demonstration and testing process (covered by work in work-package WP6). This will be discussed in more detail in the relevant deliverable (D3.7 *“Interaction Scenarios”*).

Section 2 presents a brief summary of theoretical work on interaction modelling used as a framework for ideation of control and feedback functions. Section 3 recaps the final state of the functional specifications for the UI derived from work in task T3.2 (*“Scenario-based co-design of interaction concepts”*). In this section, each use-case is handled in its own subsection. Here we also highlight which subset of functions are implemented in the demonstrators associated with this deliverable. Finally, we present the actual designs and implementations of the simulation environments and simulated UI functions for use-cases UC1 (Snow grooming), UC2 (Logistics) and UC3 (Construction) in sections 4, 5 and 6, respectively.

2 Interaction model

Based on the sender-receiver model in communication theory [1], we used interaction modelling to describe how the technical system responds to identified information requirements in various scenarios of machine operation. In this research, the technical system consists of the machine, including its structure, sensors, controllers, and actuators, and the human-machine interface (HMI), that uses data on system states from various internal and external sources to provide information (sender) to the operator (receiver). As HMIs are sensitive to distinct ways of interaction, operators also can send information to the receiving HMI. However, in this first phase of interaction concepts we focused on the first relation, by defining how information can be presented to the operator. Based on the developed modality framework, reported in deliverable D4.3. “Interaction Sequence Model”, this utilized three levels of description. Level one depicts what information is presented, e.g., raw sensor data, or (more likely) pre-processed data from various sources. Level two defines how the information is presented, which covers several subjects. This level clarifies, (1) where the information is presented (device, location in the cabin, location in the virtual user interface), (2) which modality is used (e.g., visual, acoustic, haptic modality, as well as the presentation technique, e.g., visual graphic, animation, vibration pattern), and (3) details the design of the information presentation. This design explores and defines all the associated designable degrees of freedom. Eventually level 3 defines how this information presentation behaves in relation to changes in system states or operator input.

Figure 1: Methodology for establishing the list of control and feedback functions of interest

The process for the functional analysis conducted below in Section 3 with the aim of designing the envisioned control and feedback functions is the following (see also Figure 1): Any event in a vision scenario (described in deliverable D3.7 “Interaction Scenarios”) requires the implementation of a control function (i.e., the operator acts on a user interface (UI) element to trigger and control an action executed by the vehicle, tool or UI itself), the implementation of a feedback function (i.e., the UI provides feedback elaborated by the vehicle’s internal software on the basis of acquired sensor values and internal processing), or the implementation of both.

Figure 1: Interaction model used to define component control and feedback functions

A control function can be fully described by the UI elements that are used to execute it, the output values of interaction with these UI elements, the mapping of these output values to tool setpoints, and the tool executing the action (orange pathway in Figure 1). A feedback function can be fully described by the sensors or algorithms producing the input data, the output values of these sensors or algorithms, the mapping of these output values to display element output values, and the display element providing the feedback (blue pathway in Figure 1). Thus, the description of control and feedback function implementations in Sections 4, 5 and 6 will respectively detail each of these components and the algorithms tying them together.

The analysis of the vision scenarios presented in Section 3 for use-cases UC1 (Snow grooming), UC2 (Logistics) and UC3 (Construction) respectively yields a set of unique control and feedback functions for each use-case. The initial set of functions presented in the first version of this deliverable was revised and summarized, grouping certain functions and removing functions which no longer appear relevant as the co-design process continued and more precise input was gathered from all stakeholders.

For UC1 (Snow grooming), these functions are summarized in Table 1 and Table 2 in Section 3.1.2. Similarly, for UC2 (Logistics), summary tables (Table 3 and Table 4) are provided in Section 3.2.2. The summary tables Table 5 and Table 6 for UC3 (Construction) are provided in Section 3.3.2. Each function is identified using a unique function key, following the naming convention "C" for "control" or "F" for "feedback", followed by the use-case number and the function number. This convention is used in the rest of the document for easy and concise reference when discussing implementations.

The discussion of control function implementations relevant to the design of the demonstrators is presented in Section 4.2.2 for UC1 (Snow grooming), in Section 5.2.2 for UC2 (Logistics) and in Section 6.2.2 for UC3 (Construction). Similarly, the discussion of feedback function implementations relevant to the design of the demonstrators is presented in Sections 4.3.2, 5.3.2 and 6.3.2.

3 XR UI Function Specification

3.1 Use-case 1: Snow grooming

3.1.1 Scenario analysis

Task T3.2 “*Scenario-based Co-Design of Interaction Concepts*” provided a set of two scenarios for the snow grooming use-case: a “*realistic*” scenario focused on control and feedback functions implementable in-vehicle in the short term, and a “*visionary*” scenario focused on a more long-term perspective of a potentially teleoperated vehicle. Initially, we decomposed the scenario events into implied control and feedback functions for each of these scenarios. However, it became apparent that the implementation of several of the XR UI functions for the visionary scenario are too complex to be feasible in the scope of THEIA^{XR}, hence we consider primarily the functions derived from the realistic scenario. For each of these drafts, we proceeded to decompose the scenario events into implied component control and feedback actions. This formed the basis for our collective ideation of control and feedback functions described in Sections 4.2 and 4.3. This decomposition of the scenarios into functions is reported in detail in the first version of the present deliverable “*Interaction Concepts (first version)*” (submitted 27/03/2024). In the following, we present a recap of the final set of functions considered for the simulation demonstrators.

3.1.2 Final XR UI function specification for UC1

We iteratively refined the initial control functions list by generalizing and grouping similar functions, removing or amending functions deemed unnecessary by operators in subsequent co-design workshops, and removing or amending functions deemed too complex or impractical to implement by technology providers. This process yields a set of consolidated control function specifications for the simulation demonstrator of UC1 presented below. The functions are color coded, green indicating they are entirely implemented in simulation, orange indicating they are partially implemented, and grey indicating they are not implemented. Details are provided in the “*In simulation?*” column of the table:

KEY	CONTROL FUNCTION	PARTNER	IN SIMULATION?
C11	Operator starts the engine	PRIN TTC	YES: This function is state-of-the-art
C12	Operator drives the vehicle with/without transporting snow	HAP TTC	YES: This function is state-of-the-art, using the novel haptic track controls unit
C13	Operator adjusts the blade settings to collect/move/deposit snow	HAP TTC	YES: Multiple blade control kinematics are explored using the 6DoF primary haptic joystick.
C14	Operator adjusts the tiller settings	HAP TTC	YES: This function is state-of-the-art, using the 6DoF primary haptic joystick as a conventional 2DoF input device.
C15	Operator toggles the haptics components	HAP TTC	Partial: Software plans for toggles, but to keep the simulation manageable, haptic behaviors are switched on by default.
C16	Operator runs the “ <i>ground visualization</i> ” system (projection of light grid on the ground to indicate snow depth)	N.A.	NO: Preliminary testing and operator workshops tend to indicate that this feature is both more complex to implement and less useful to operators than anticipated.
C17	Operator toggles “ <i>poor visibility support</i> ” system	TTC	NO: The system is on by default
C18	Operator toggles 3D visualization of vehicle position on slope	TTC	Partial: Currently on by default, but the software design would allow simple toggling
C19	Operator operates the winch	N.A.	NO: No winch in simulation, no novel XR UI planned for this function

C110	Operator activates smart spotlight	N.A.	NO: Discussion with operators shows that the utility of the smart spotlight is uncertain.
C111	Operator directs smart spotlight	N.A.	NO: Discussion with operators shows that the utility of the smart spotlight is uncertain.
C112	Operator provides input to the navigation system	TTC	NO: Navigation system prototypes use preset targets

Table 1: Final list of control functions for UC1

Applying the same process to the feedback functions, we obtain the list below:

KEY	FEEDBACK FUNCTION	PARTNER	IN SIMULATION?
F11	Inform operator of successful start and safe machine state.	TUD TTC	Partial: The snow groomer is started and in a safe state at the simulation start. Displays and light bars implicitly inform about safe state.
F12	Inform operator about vehicle width and alignment relative to trajectory, targets, slope and horizon line.	HAP TUG TTC	YES: Projection guides mapped on simulation display, display of vehicle 3D model on slope model (TUG, TTC), Haptic vehicle heading controller (HAP).
F13	“Safe path home” guidance	HAP	YES: Torque guidance in haptic track controls, environment projections
F14	Inform operator about current blade settings and state, as well as discrepancies between them and calculated blade settings	HAP TTC PRIN	Partial: Haptic blade-ground collision avoidance on the primary arm.
F15	Inform operator about recommended speed.	HAP TTC	YES: Torque guidance in haptic track controls.
F16	Inform operator about current and target snow depth in front of the vehicle.	TUD	Partial: Cross-section projection (only in TUD interaction lab mock-up cabin).
F17	Inform operator about the presence, distance to, and heading towards obstacles in the vicinity	TUD HAP	YES: Obstacle location and distance on light bars; Haptic brake assistance.
F18	Warn operator that winch is required	N.A.	NO: No winch in the simulation as the implementation is too complex.
F19	Inform operator about winch cable path or direction	N.A.	NO: No winch in the simulation as the implementation is too complex.
F20	Inform operator about the presence and direction towards a hazard in the winch operating area	N.A.	NO: No winch in the simulation as the implementation is too complex.

Table 2: Final list of feedback functions for UC1

3.2 Use-case 2: Logistics

3.2.1 Scenario analysis

Once again, task T3.2 “*Scenario-based Co-Design of Interaction Concepts*” provided a set of two scenarios for the logistics use-case: a “*realistic*” scenario focused on control and feedback functions implementable in-vehicle in the short term, and a “*visionary*” scenario focused on a more long-term perspective of a potentially teleoperated vehicle. However, given the short-term focus of our logistics partners on moving to remote-controlled (RC) reachstacker operation, these scenarios were adapted to form a single scenario focused on reachstacker remote operation (the “*realistic RC*” scenario), which is handled below. A “*visionary RC*” scenario was also created, but it focuses more on additional benefits of a potential XR UI in teleoperating vehicles from multiple harbor terminals, and thus goes beyond the scope of the simulated demo

implementations proposed herein. Once again, the decomposition of the scenarios into functions is reported in detail in the first version of the present deliverable “*Interaction Concepts*” (submitted 27/03/2024). In the following, we present a recap of the final set of functions considered for the simulation demonstrator.

3.2.2 Final XR UI function specification for UC2

We iteratively refined the initial control functions list by generalizing and grouping similar functions, removing or amending functions deemed unnecessary by operators in the co-design workshops, and removing or amending functions deemed too complex or impractical to implement by technology providers. This process yields a set of consolidated control function specifications for the simulation demonstrator of use-case UC2 (Logistics) presented below. As is described in more detail in Section 5.1 below, for practical implementation reasons, the simulations for use-case UC2 were split into three distinct implementations, each focusing on different interaction aspects. Thus, the “In simulation?” column in the tables below also specifies in which of the three simulation environments the given function is implemented.

KEY	CONTROL FUNCTION	PARTNER	IN SIMULATION?
C21	Operator logs in and identifies themselves in the RC console system	N.A.	NO: Interaction with the RC console itself is beyond the scope of the simulations.
C22	Operator checks that the RC console indicator lights are working	N.A.	NO: Interaction with the RC console itself is beyond the scope of the simulations.
C23	Operator contacts service personnel	N.A.	NO: Interaction with the RC console itself is beyond the scope of the simulations.
C24	Operator connects/disconnects to/from the reachstacker	N.A.	NO: Interaction with the RC console itself is beyond the scope of the simulations.
C25	Operator switches on the working lights of the reachstacker	N.A.	NO: The function is state of the art.
C26	Operator switches on the engine	N.A.	NO: Since the function is state-of-the-art, the simulations start with the engine already running.
C27	Operator switches the machine to auto or RC mode	VTT	PARTIAL: User provides confirmation that work is complete and the simulator automatically switches to auto mode.
C28	Operator manually drives the machine	KAL	YES: Manual driving is implemented in the KAL simulation (state of the art). All driving in the VTT and HAP simulations is automated.
C29	Operator maneuvers boom and spreader	HAP, VTT, KAL	YES: HAP simulation uses 6DoF joystick input. VTT & KAL simulations use state-of-the-art 2-axis joystick and button input.
C210	Operator engages/disengages the twistlocks	HAP, KAL, VTT	YES: All simulations include state-of-the-art joystick button press input for twistlock operation.
C211	Operator toggles the twistlock auto-lock functions	VTT, KAL, HAP	YES: The KAL simulation includes a touchscreen toggle for the auto-lock function. The function is pre-activated in the VTT simulator. The HAP simulation uses a keyboard toggle for the function.
C212	Operator adjusts cabin camera position	VTT	YES: The VTT simulator provides gesture-based camera position control.
C213	Operator triggers emergency stop	VTT, KAL, HAP	YES: The VTT simulator features a dedicated button on a keyboard acting as emergency stop. The KAL simulator features a dedicated emergency stop switch. The HAP simulator features a physical deadman and emergency

			stop which interrupts input/output (IO) through the 6DoF joystick.
C214	Operator switches camera view	VTT	YES: The VTT simulator features a gesture-based camera view control
C215	Operator toggles minimap	N.A.	NO: Only the KAL simulator features a basic minimap, which is always toggled on (requiring no operator input)
C216	Operator toggles XR visualizations	N.A.	NO: To keep simulator operation manageable, XR visualizations are active by default in all simulators.
C217	Operator puts the vehicle into standby	N.A.	NO: The function is only marginally relevant to THEIA ^{XR}
C218	Operator calls up personal performance dashboard and job playback	N.A.	NO: It was decided that this function would be designed later, for implementation in an actual vehicle.

Table 3: Final list of control functions for UC2

Applying the same process to the feedback functions, we obtain the list below:

KEY	FEEDBACK FUNCTION	PARTNER	IN SIMULATION?
F21	Inform operator of successful login into RC console system	N.A.	NO: No RC console interaction in the simulations
F22	Inform operator that RC console indicator lights are functional	N.A.	NO: No RC console interaction in the simulations
F23	Provide audio communication to service personnel	N.A.	NO: No RC console interaction in the simulations
F24	Inform operator of successful connection to the reachstacker	N.A.	NO: No RC console interaction in the simulations
F25	Inform operator of preset vehicle settings associated with operator ID, as well as their successful application	HAP	PARTIAL: In the HAP simulation, a dedicated “joystick configurator” environment is implemented, providing the opportunity for exploring customized settings for the control devices.
F26	Provide operator with clear view and earshot to machine operation and vicinity, through multiple camera views of vehicle.	VTT	YES: In VTT/HAP simulations.
F27	Inform operator of vehicle operational/dysfunctional state.	KAL HAP	PARTIAL: The KAL simulation features state of the art visual and audio disfunction warnings. The HAP simulation features haptic vehicle disfunction warnings
F28	Inform operator about successful switch between auto and RC mode.		NO: The successful switch is implicit in the vehicle behavior in the VTT simulation. The KAL simulation features only manual driving. The HAP simulation features no driving.
F29	Inform operator about list of assigned orders, pending jobs, job selection, job details & overview.	KAL	YES: This feature is implemented in the KAL simulation.
F210	Provide operator with the layout or minimap of the port in the vicinity of the vehicle	KAL	PARTIAL: The KAL simulation features a basic minimap indicating direction towards the target on the terminal display.
F211	Alert operator to approaching machine	VTT	YES: In VTT simulation.

F212	Inform operator about safe space available for extending the spreader	VTT HAP	YES: In VTT and HAP simulations.
F213	Inform operator about current set spreader size	N.A.	NO: Spreader size is implicitly shown via visual feedback through camera views.
F214	Inform operator about horizontal and vertical distance between twist locks and container corners	VTT HAP	YES: In VTT and HAP simulations.
F215	Inform operator that twist locks can be safely engaged/disengaged, i.e. that the spreader has reached a suitable position for picking/releasing the container. (Applies to manual and autolock functions)	KAL VTT HAP	YES: In all simulations.
F216	Inform operator that twist locks have successfully been engaged/disengaged. (Applies to manual and autolock functions)	KAL VTT HAP	YES: In all simulations.
F217	Inform operator that vicinity is clear for reversing.	N.A.	NO: Although not explicitly implemented, this is implicit in the rear-view camera.
F218	Inform operator that boom and spreader are in a suitable position for driving / transport.	VTT	YES: In the VTT simulation.
F219	Inform operator about truck ID in loading order, and ID of truck currently being loaded.	N.A.	NO: No ID verification or order number mechanism in the simulations.
F220	Inform operator about vehicle ideal loading position and orientation relative to truck being loaded, as well as discrepancies between current and ideal position for loading.	N.A.	NO: Automated driving in VTT/HAP simulation implies ideal vehicle positioning.
F221	Inform operator that the container has been sufficiently lowered to allow release.	HAP	YES: The HAP simulation explicitly provides this information through ground contact feedback (force and vibration).
F222	Inform operator that the spreader has cleared the container.	HAP	YES: In HAP simulation.
F223	Inform operator of the presence of persons in the vicinity of the vehicle	VTT	YES: In VTT simulation.
F224	Inform operator that spreader has reached an end-stop or target position.	HAP	YES: In HAP simulation.
F225	Inform operator that the job is complete.	KAL	YES: In KAL simulation.
F226	Inform operator that RS is safely stopped and ready for disconnect.	N.A.	NO: No RC console interaction in the simulation.
F227	Inform operator that RC console is disconnected from reachstacker.	N.A.	NO: No RC console interaction in the simulation.
F228	Provide dashboard of the vehicle's parameters (fuel, oil temperature, gearbox temperature)	KAL	YES: In KAL simulation.
F229	Inform operator about distance and ideal route to target location.	VTT KAL	YES: In VTT and KAL simulations.

F230	Inform operator about current auto driving functions being executed (acceleration, braking, steering)	VTT	YES: In VTT simulation.
F231	Inform operator about relative position of objects, persons, vehicles or targets (container, truck) in the environment.	VTT	YES: In VTT simulation.
F232	Inform operator about container weight and/or center of mass.	VTT HAP	YES: In VTT and HAP simulations.
F233	Project the container limits or ideal loading position on the ground	VTT	YES: In VTT simulation
F234	Inform operator that vehicle has successfully been put into standby.	N.A.	NO: No RC console interaction in the simulation
F235	Provide operator with a personal performance dashboard	N.A.	NO: No RC console interaction in the simulation
F236	Provide operator with a fast-forward playback of the day's driving path	N.A.	NO: No RC console interaction in the simulation
F237	Inform operator of successful logout of the RC desk.	N.A.	NO: No RC console interaction in the simulation

Table 4: Final list of feedback functions for UC2

3.3 Use-case 3: Construction

3.3.1 Scenario analysis

As with both other use-cases, task T3.2 “Scenario-based Co-Design of Interaction Concepts” provided a set of two scenarios for the excavator use-case: a “realistic” scenario focused on control and feedback functions implementable in-vehicle in the short term, and a “visionary” scenario focused on a more long-term perspective of a potentially teleoperated vehicle. For the purposes of the present deliverable, the focus remains on the “realistic” scenario, with control and feedback functions implemented in the vehicle cabin. The decomposition of the scenarios into functions is reported in detail in the first version of the present deliverable “Interaction Concepts” (submitted 27/03/2024). In the following, we present a recap of the final set of functions considered for the simulation demonstrator.

3.3.2 Final XR UI function specification for UC3

We iteratively refined the initial control functions list by generalizing and grouping similar functions, removing or amending functions deemed unnecessary by operators in the co-design workshops, and removing or amending functions deemed too complex or impractical to implement by technology providers. This process yields a set of consolidated control function specifications for the simulation demonstrator of UC3 presented below:

KEY	CONTROL FUNCTION	PARTNER	IN SIMULATION?
C31	Operator starts the engine, powers down the vehicle, or locks all moving parts	TUD CREA	YES (state of the art): using physical buttons placed in the TUD mock-up cabin.
C32	Operator drives and orients the excavator	TUD CREA	YES (state of the art): using a pair of pedals in the TUD mock-up cabin.
C33	Operator controls drive, carriage, boom, arm and bucket to maneuver on site and effect surface profile.	TUD CREA	YES (State-of-the-art) Using a pair of CAN joysticks
C34	Operator calls up a visualization of the planned excavation on screen and manipulates view angle and	TUD	YES: Off-the-shelf touchscreen interfaced with the simulation PC

	data augmentation in the visualization to familiarity with the task.		
C35	Operator creates CAD model of the planned pit	TUD	YES: Tool movement and main GUI
C36	Operator adjusts views in terminal display switching between camera and 3D machine and environment views.	TUD	YES: Touchscreen, Physical control panel
C37	Operator activates collision warning and surface assistance	TUD CREA	YES: Touchscreen, Physical control panel
C38	Operator adjusts modality and salience of warning according to his needs or situational conditions before the mission	TUD	YES: Touchscreen, Physical control panel
C310	Select between single panel display and split screen views & view contents	TUD	YES: Touchscreen

Table 5: Final list of control functions for UC3

Applying the same process to the feedback functions, we obtain the list below:

KEY	FEEDBACK FUNCTION	PARTNER	IN SIMULATION?
F31	Inform operator about vehicle and assistance system functional state	TUD CREA	NO: No failure scenarios in the simulation
F32	Inform operator of intended excavation geometry.	TUD CREA	YES: Laser projection in simulation
F33	Inform operator of distance to the target excavation depth.	TUD CREA	YES: Matrix display and light bars
F34	Provide operator with an unobstructed view of the surrounding (Optional).	TUD CREA	YES: Video streams to the tablet
F35	Inform operator about detected obstacles in the vicinity	TUD CREA	YES: Indication in the GUI, Light bars
F36	Inform operator of an immediate danger in the vicinity.	TUD CREA	YES: Light bars
F37	Inform operator of buried hazard (e.g. cables, pipes) in excavation area	TUD CREA	YES: Matrix display, Display on the tablet
F38	Inform operator of successful activation of environment warning system.	TUD CREA	NO
F39	Inform persons around of excavation in progress and imminent machine movements.	TUD CREA	NO: This function will be showcased on the real vehicle
F310	Inform persons around that the object detection system has registered them (optional)	TUD	YES: Light bars around the outside of the cabin
F311	Inform operator that the tool movement is within intended digging area.	TUD CREA	YES: Projections, Matrix display
F312	Inform operator about the location of the edges of the trench/pit.	TUD CREA	YES: Projections, Tablet GUI
F313	Inform operator about ideal unloading area and zone to be left free for vehicle tracks to drive on (optional)	TUD CREA	NO: Not relevant in a manually operated machine.
F314	Inform operator about reaching desired excavation depth.	TUD CREA	YES: Matrix display, Tablet GUI, Light bars

Table 6: Final list of feedback functions for UC3

4 Use-case 1: Snow groomer

4.1 Simulation environment

The playable demonstration for the snow grooming use-case were developed under the heading of Creanex, who built a virtual environment replicating realistic snow grooming environments, a simulated vehicle, as well as providing simulated UI elements and interfaces for external physical UI elements.

The general hardware framework presented in deliverable D5.6 *“Multimodal Immersive Cockpit”* (submitted 31/03/2025) has been adapted to feature the subset of devices specific to the requirements of use-case UC1. Physically, the demonstrator was implemented using a Prinoth Leitwolf cabin modified to host all relevant hardware components (see Figure 2). These are the TTC control unit, the Haption haptic primary joystick and track controls unit, the TUD environment light display, and terminal displays. The physical hardware components developed in the THEIA^{XR} project for interfacing with the simulation are described in detail in deliverable D5.6 *“Multimodal Immersive Cockpit”* (submitted 31/03/2025).

Figure 2: Prinoth demonstrator cabin interfaced with Creanex simulation at the InterAlpin fair

The snow groomer simulation builds on the Creanex simulator platform. The virtual work environment and simulation scene has been created from real slope data provided by Prinoth. The terrain data model was converted into an “.fbx” file, which was then imported into the Unity3D editor and further worked on to make it into a so-called Unity terrain. The google earth screen capture as a reference, the slope model and the created Unity terrain model are presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Simulated terrain of Ladurns skiing area based on real-world data provided by Prinoth

A virtual model of a Prinoth Leitwolf snow groomer is controlled by the operator and interacts with the virtual environment through a custom physics simulation (see Figure 4). The physics simulation is based on rigid-body dynamics including interaction with the environment, meaning that there are contacts between the machine and the ground and on each contact point there is a pair of forces based on which the machine moves.

Figure 4: Prinoth snow groomer in simulated environment

The top-level architecture is presented in Figure 5 below. The interaction models used by the physics simulation are converted or manually created from the visual models. Control panels are used to operate the

machine in the physics simulation. After every simulation step the state in physics is updated to the visualization system.

Figure 5: Architecture of the Creanex simulator platform.

The Creanex simulation platform and available features for sensor simulations and other capabilities are presented in deliverable D4.9 “*Concept of virtual user interface (final version)*”.

4.2 Control functions (input)

The analysis of the vision scenarios presented in Section 3.1 above yields the list of individual control functions summarized in Table 1. Below, we discuss the functions already implemented in part or in full in the state of the art, followed by a description of all proposed novel implementations.

4.2.1 State of the art

In this section, we briefly cover how existing control functions are implemented in snow groomers. This will serve as a baseline for understanding proposed improvements over the state-of-the-art in the simulation interactions described in Section 4.2.2 below. It also describes how unchanged control functions that are included within the playable demonstrations are implemented.

The operator starts the vehicle using a push-button or key-switch (C11) drives the vehicle using the right-hand pair of track controls and throttle pedal (C12).

Figure 6: Existing mapping between joystick controls and blade motions

Currently, blade pose is controlled by using the main joystick's two axes of rotation (C13) combined with one of two push-buttons, which map joystick rotations either to blade height and roll, blade tilt and pan, or left or right blade- wing opening and closing (see Figure 6). The joystick-in-joystick feature (see Figure 7) allows four simultaneous blade movements. Joystick angles linearly map to blade element angular velocity in each case.

Figure 7: Joystick button designations and joystick-in-joystick features

The multiple functions of the tiller (see Figure 8) are controlled using combinations of push-buttons on the primary joystick handle, the joystick rotations, as well as potentiometers and the joystick-in-joystick JJ-1/JJ-3 feature (see Figure 6 and Figure 7) on the primary joystick (C14).

Figure 8: Controlled tiller functions

Currently, collecting and transporting snow to build or repair surfaces (C12, C13 and C14) involve a combination of driving the vehicle to a location with excess snow as well as adjusting the blade and tiller settings to separate a certain amount of snow from the surface and push it to the target location.

In vehicles equipped with 3D visualization (see Figure 10 below) or navigation systems, these are activated using the buttons on the relevant displays (C18, C112).

When winching (C19), operators start by manually anchoring the vehicle to a relevant anchor point above the slope. Operators drive as usual, activate or stop the winch, then continuously adjust the pull exerted on the winch cable during operation, using controls on the control unit and primary joystick. Furthermore, depending on the vehicle, operators may be able to adjust the rotation behavior of the winch tower to better control the cable path. When winching, it is possible to have up to 1.2km of winch cable between the vehicle and the anchor point sitting on the top of the grooming area. Therefore, additionally to the winch force setting, the operator has to make sure that the cable doesn't hit or get tangled in objects surrounding the operational area. Furthermore, the operator has to minimize the damage caused by dragging the cable over the already groomed surface.

Although there is no "smart spotlight" yet as state-of-the-art on snow groomers, vehicles are equipped with a manually controlled spotlight which can be switched on and off and directed using a dedicated handle in the cabin roof (C110, C111).

4.2.2 Control functions prototyped in simulation

This section describes the innovations beyond the state of the art that were prototyped in simulation by the THEIA^{XR} partners, grouped by the control function that is to be achieved. As described in Section 2 above, a control function can be characterized by the input device(s) it leverages, the values (machine setpoints, UI states and variables, etc.) it controls, and how the input device degrees of freedom or states map to the controlled values' states. Therefore, for each of the control functions described below, we begin by presenting a summary table for these descriptors, followed by more details about the physical and algorithmic implementation of the control function in text below. The "Mappings" column in the summary table is only relevant in the case where multiple different mappings are being explored in the simulation, otherwise it contains the mention "Unique Mapping", which means only a single mapping has been implemented, which is that described in the detail text below. In addition, the "Partner" column in the function summary table identifies the project partner(s) responsible for the implementation of the physical infrastructure for fulfilling the function as well as the algorithmics underpinning the function execution. The partner responsible for the simulation environment (in the present use-case, Creanex) is not mentioned unless the function is entirely fulfilled in the simulation, as it is implicit that all functions discussed in this deliverable interact with the simulation.

4.2.2.1 C11 - Operator starts the engine, powers down the vehicle, or locks all moving parts

Summary

Partner	Input device	Controlled values	Mapping(s)
PRIN TTC	State-of-the-art engine start button and gas pedal	Engine on/off (binary) Engine throttle (binary)	Unique mapping

Table 7: C11 Control function summary table

The user presses the engine start button to start the virtual engine, and pushes down the gas pedal to enable the throttle. Both devices are state-of-the-art components of a Prinoth snow groomer, and send a CAN message which is received by the TTC control unit, then relayed to the Creanex simulation. This function simply replicates the state of the art in physical snow groomers. The shared data between the systems is sent as messages over CAN bus as described in deliverable D5.3 "Visualization and Interaction Infrastructure" (due M30).

4.2.2.2 C12 - Operator drives the vehicle (with/without transporting snow)

Summary

Partner	Input device	Controlled values	Mapping(s)
HAP TTC	Haptic track controls unit	Left track velocity setpoint Right track velocity setpoint	Unique mapping

Table 8: C12 Control function summary table

The haptic track control unit calibrates the zero position of the levers at startup. During operation, the user then sets the deflection angles of the left and right levers as desired. This deflection angle is compared to the maximum lever deflection angle set in the Haptics ECU software, yielding a relative angle as a floating-point value between -1 and 1. These relative angles are communicated to the TTC control unit as per the protocol described in deliverable D5.3 “*Visualization and Interaction Infrastructure*” (due M30). The TTC control unit then forwards them as the setpoint for the track velocities in the Creanex simulation, using the CAN messages described in D5.3.

4.2.2.3 C13 - Operator adjusts the blade settings to collect/move/deposit snow

Summary

Partner	Input device	Controlled values	Mapping(s)
HAP TTC CREA	Primary 6DoF Haptic Joystick	Blade roll, yaw, pitch Blade raising/lowering Left and right blade wing angles	(A) Standard (B) 6DoF input

Table 9: C13 Control function summary table

Because of the complexity of simulating snow, the Creanex simulation provides a limited area within which snow can be moved by the virtual snowgroomer. The Unity terrain surface is large and it cannot be modified in real time, so a part of the slope model is replaced by a separate triangular mesh. The mesh is a grid and the Z-coordinate of each grid vertex can be modified in real time.

The selected input device kinematics are defined in a configuration message sent by the TTC control unit to the Haptics ECU on start-up. The Haptics ECU triggers a calibration of the 6DoF arm on startup, recording the zero pose (translation and rotation of the handle at rest). The Haptics ECU and low-level haptics controllers then handle locking, releasing and limiting of the range of the relevant DoF for the chosen input kinematics. The cartesian axis values are computed as relative floating-point values between -1 and 1, and send to the TTC control unit as per the messaging protocol described in deliverable D5.3 “*Visualization and Interaction Infrastructure*” (due M30). Below is a description of the two possible kinematic modes for interacting with the snow groomer blade.

(A) Standard:

See the section on state of the art above (Section 4.2.1). Here we lock all DoF except for axis 4 and axis 5 rotation on the primary haptic device, yielding a conventional 2-axis joystick behavior as already exists in snow groomers. Handle buttons are used to switch between DoF of the blade being controlled as per the state of the art. Since the CAN output of the Prinoth handle is completely decoupled from the 6-axis primary joystick (see deliverable D5.6 “*Multimodal Immersive Cockpit*” for hardware details), the TTC control unit transmits the relevant button states recorded from the CAN bus back to the Haptics ECU in the sensor data message (buttons JJ2, JB7 and JB8, see Figure 6). Based on this, if the standard input mapping is selected, the Haptics ECU processes the button input to map the joystick x and y rotation values to the blade translation and rotation velocity setpoint values for the relevant axes as per the state-of-the-art.

(B) 6DoF Blade control

As with standard control, all motions of the handle map to velocity setpoints for the blade, to conserve a familiar “feel” for the operators, and to minimize the required motion amplitudes. The 6DoF blade control concept is schematically represented in Figure 9. The three handle rotations map directly to the three rotations of the main blade. Similarly, the handle up and down motions map to the main blade vertical

translation axis. When near the origin of the joystick workspace, it becomes possible to move the joystick left and right (joystick Y axis) by pushing past a virtual “latch” generated through a force-feedback algorithm implementing a virtual spring. The joystick handle then ends up in a new resting position ten centimeters to the left or right of the workspace origin, in which it is only possible to rotate the handle around its z-axis to control the left or right blade wing rotation, or to push the handle back towards the workspace origin (again, pushing past a virtual latch) to return to controlling the main blade degrees of freedom. Figure 9 below provides an illustration of this novel control scheme.

Figure 9: 6DoF blade control concept

4.2.2.4 C14 - Operator adjusts the tiller settings

Summary

Partner	Input device	Controlled values	Mapping(s)
HAP TTC	Primary 6DoF Haptic Joystick	All 9 tiller DoF	Unique mapping

Table 10: C14 Control function summary table

In the simulation, tiller settings are purely for demonstration of input kinematics and have no effect on the virtual snow. Since the tiller has 9 degrees of freedom, of which many do not intuitively map to motions in cartesian space (e.g., tiller pressure, cutting speed, etc.), it is not obvious that implementing novel control kinematics for the tiller might simplify the task for operators compared to the state of the art.

Here, we proceed identically as for mapping (A) for the blade control, locking all DoF except for axis 4 and axis 5 rotation on the primary haptic device, yielding a conventional 2-axis joystick behavior as already exists in snow groomers (see Section 4.2.2.3). The Haptics ECU notifies the joystick deflections on both axes to the TTC control unit, which forwards them to the tiller control based on operator button presses, replicating state-of-the-art control of the tiller.

4.2.2.5 C15 - Operator toggles the haptics components

Summary

Partner	Input device	Controlled values	Mapping(s)
TTC TUD PRIN	Touch screen Or Button array	Activation of the four haptic feedback components (joystick force feedback, track controls force feedback, joystick vibration, and track controls vibration)	Unique mapping
HAP	Deadman switches	Activation of force feedback	Unique mapping

Table 11: C15 Control function summary table

4.2.2.5.1 Touch-screen / Button toggle input

The haptics ECU software supports independent toggling of the force and vibrotactile feedback on both haptic input devices. Associated physical or touchscreen toggles have not been implemented yet, but could easily be added to utilize this function if required in ulterior tests.

4.2.2.5.2 Deadman switches

While not initially designed as a toggle for haptics functions, the deadman switches incorporated in the haptic track controls unit as well as the primary joystick inherently act as such (see deliverable D5.6 “*Multimodal Immersive Cockpit*” for detailed hardware descriptions). Indeed, disengaging the deadman on a track controls lever or on the primary joystick handle immediately inhibits power delivery to the force-feedback motors, thus disabling any force-feedback behavior. This process takes place at a low level in the haptics power-supply electronics.

4.2.2.6 C18 - Operator toggles 3D visualization of vehicle position on slope

Summary

Partner	Input device	Controlled values	Mapping(s)
TTC	Touch-screen	directly	Display of position of vehicle in a simulated environment based on GPS coordinates
TUG	connected to the control unit		Unique mapping

Table 12: C18 Control function summary table

The display within the cabin displays the current position of the snow groomer in a simulated version of the same environment where the snow groomer is being deployed. In the current version, this information is directly displayed on the screen, so no toggling is yet available. The simulation is running on the central controller in the machine and displayed on one of the monitors connected to the central processor. The application for the simulation and the calculation of the position of the snow groomer based on the GPS coordinates is performed in the cabin on the central processor.

4.3 Modes of information presentation (feedback)

The list of individual feedback functions resulting from the analysis presented in Section 3.1 is summarized in Table 2. Below, we discuss the functions already implemented in part or in full in the state of the art, followed by a description of all proposed novel implementations.

4.3.1 State of the art

In this section, we briefly cover how the feedback functions considered that are currently fulfilled by snow groomers are implemented. This will serve as a baseline for understanding proposed improvements in the interactions described in Section 4.3.2 below. It will also serve as a specification for implementation of unchanged control functions that need to be included within the playable demonstrations.

Operators rely on visual inspection, feedback from maintenance staff and information from the vehicle dashboard to assess the safe state of the machine (F11). Operators rely on the sound of the engine and responsiveness of track controls to assess successful engine start (F11).

To manipulate the blade and tiller, operators rely on visual line of sight to the blade through the windshield, and line of sight to the tiller through rear view mirrors and, when it is available, a rear-facing camera showing a video stream on the in-vehicle display (F14, F17). This rear view also allows them to assess the success of repairs made to a damaged slope. The blade alignment can also be visualized in on-board software systems such as that shown in Figure 10.

Currently, operators may have access to a 3D visualization of the vehicle on a reconstructed terrain model based on snow depth measurement and GNSS data (see Figure 10). This scan of the immediate vicinity can

help navigation and operation (F13, F17). This visualization would however not react to dynamic events and the presence of unknown and unplanned hazards and obstacles.

Figure 10: Leica iCON alpine snow measurement visualization system¹

Furthermore, the snow depth measurement system can be used to notify the operator of excess snow digging depth, in addition to direct line-of-sight to the terrain in the vicinity (F16).

Regarding winch operation, currently, operators know that the winch is successfully anchored at the moment they anchor it, and assume it remains so when the anchor is out of sight (F18). The torque exerted by the winch motor is indicated to the operator on the in-vehicle display. The only means that operators have for assessing the winch cable path as well as the presence of hazards in the winch operating area is direct line of sight, whereby the winch cable is often poorly visible and much too long to be visible in its entirety.

4.3.2 Feedback functions prototyped in simulation

This section describes the feedback functions going beyond the state of the art that are prototyped in simulation by the THEIA^{XR} partners, grouped by the feedback function that is to be achieved. As described in Section 2 above, a feedback function can be characterized by the output device(s) used to display the information, the values (machine states, environment states, sensor values, UI states and variables, etc.) being show to the operator, and how the sensors or internal algorithms map the displayed values to the output devices' states or degrees of freedom. Therefore, for each of the feedback functions described below, we begin by presenting a summary table for these descriptors, followed by more details about the physical and algorithmic implementation of the feedback function in text below. The "Mappings" and "Partner" columns in the summary table follow the same logic as the one previously described for the control functions (see Section 4.2.2 above).

4.3.2.1 F11 - Inform operator of successful engine start and safe machine state.

Summary

Partner	Output device	Displayed values	Mapping(s)
TUD	Light bars	Machine state safe/unsafe (binary)	Unique mapping
TTC	Display		Unique mapping
HAP	Haptic track controls and primary joystick vibrotactile actuators	Engine stopped/started (binary)	Unique mapping

Table 13: F11 Feedback function summary table

¹ Source: Leica Geosystems <https://leica-geosystems.com/products/machine-control-systems/leica-icon-alpine>

The simulated snow groomer by Creanex provides audio feedback of the motor running as would exist in a real snow groomer. The simulation assumes a safe vehicle state. However, certain feedback UI components may be triggered to react to an unsafe vehicle state triggered in a wizard-of-oz approach in order to showcase their function.

4.3.2.1.1 Light bars and terminal display

Since the simulator puts the vehicle in an OK state by default, the light bars and terminal display light up normally, implicitly indicating normal and safe vehicle operation.

4.3.2.1.2 Haptic track controls

If the haptic track controls are powered on and the vehicle engine is stopped or the throttle is disengaged (this information is relayed to the Haptics ECU by the TTC CPU via the Sensor Data message), torque feedback is applied to keep the track control levers in the zero position. This provides additional safety against unintended accelerations of the vehicle and provides an intuitive way for the operator to check whether or not the engine is running. This behavior is active by default and not toggleable via a Toggle Haptics message.

If a fault is triggered in a wizard-of-oz approach (this can be directly done on the Haptics ECU, e.g. through keyboard input), the vibrotactile actuators in both device handles emit a “WARNING_UNSAFE” vibration as per the vibration patterns described in [APPENDIX A: VIBROTACTILE FEEDBACK LIBRARY](#). This behavior is toggleable using behavior code 1 in a Toggle Haptics Message.

4.3.2.2 *F12 - Inform operator about vehicle width and alignment relative to trajectory, targets, slope and horizon line*

Summary

Partner	Output device	Displayed values	Mapping(s)
HAP	Haptic track controls torque feedback	Recommended vehicle heading	Unique mapping
HAP	Haptic track controls vibrotactile feedback	Overshoot from recommended grooming lane	Unique mapping
TUG TTC	Terminal display	Position of the snow groomer in the simulated environment	Unique mapping

Table 14: F12 Feedback function summary table

4.3.2.2.1 Haptic track controls torque feedback

For the torque feedback pertaining to vehicle guidance, we distinguish two cases: trajectory guidance based on a series of pre-computed waypoints (which may or may not be associated with a desired vehicle heading at a given waypoint), and lane-keeping guidance, which is based on similar waypoints with associated desired vehicle headings along with an on-the-fly calculation of the current deviation from the ideal trajectory. All this information is provided to the haptics ECU by the TTC CPU in the Sensor Data Message, depending on the task at hand.

Figure 11: Two cases for vehicle guidance: (A) Waypoint based path, (B) Lane-keeping

In a simple waypoint-based trajectory guidance task (Figure 11 A), we once again have two distinct cases, based on whether or not the supplied trajectory waypoints include a desired heading. If no desired heading is known (Waypoint 2 in Figure 11 A), we simply compute a current desired heading on the fly based on the vector from the current snowgroomer position to the next waypoint (this desired heading therefore updates as we move relative to the target waypoint). Otherwise, if the target heading is known (Waypoint 1 in Figure 11 A), we perform a pose interpolation via spline to compute a set of intermediary waypoints which allow for continuous adjustment of the vehicle heading.

In the second scenario where the vehicle must keep to a lane specified through its center-line, which also is a set of waypoints with associated desired headings, we apply the same heading computation based on a spline interpolation.

The computed target heading is supplied as an input to the hybrid heading and velocity controller described below. Regarding the target velocity supplied to the controller, either the system is providing a recommended vehicle velocity, in which case this is used (see function F15 in Section 4.3.2.5 below), or no recommended speed is provided, in which case the current travel speed (set by the operator) is used as a vehicle velocity setpoint.

For the purpose of this feedback function as well as others described below in the document (F13, F15 and F17), we propose a torque feedback guidance in the track control levers that gently nudges the operator towards a pre-calculated vehicle heading and velocity (see Figure 12 below).

Figure 12: Hybrid haptic feedback controller for vehicle velocity and heading

For this function, the TTC control unit sends a CONFIG message to the haptics ECU on startup, which enables the haptic track controls and a Toggle Haptics message enabling torque feedback on the track controls, and supplying behavior codes 2 to 4 (see deliverable D5.3 “Visualization and interaction infrastructure”, considering that lane-keeping takes precedence over waypoint navigation with headings, which itself takes precedence over waypoint navigation without headings).

During operation, the desired heading is compared against the current vehicle heading (sensed in simulation). This yields a heading setpoint error ϵ_θ used as input for a “Yaw rate” PID controller, which gives a vehicle rotation velocity setpoint. This vehicle rotation velocity setpoint is then compared to the estimated vehicle rotational velocity to yield a yaw rate error ϵ_ω . Together with the vehicle velocity setpoint error ϵ_v , this is used to compute a pair of track velocity setpoint errors $\Delta\hat{v}_L$ and $\Delta\hat{v}_R$. Each of these track velocity setpoint errors is independently fed into a PID controller (“HapticsController” in Figure 12), yielding a torque applied to the respective control lever. In this manner, the operator is continuously nudged towards the lever position which would command the vehicle to rotate towards the currently desired heading. The dotted lines in Figure 12 aim to represent the fact that the operator perceived both the resulting torque and current angle for each lever, using this sensory information to adjust the torque applied to each lever in a closed loop.

4.3.2.2.2 Lane keeping vibrations

We compute the deviation distance to the target lane as the magnitude of the vector connecting the current snowgroomer position to the closest point on the target lane (both of which are supplied by the TTC CPU in the Sensor Data message. Above or below a minimum distance of 350 cm (which corresponds to half a snowgroomer width plus a margin), we trigger an OUT_OF_LANE (see APPENDIX A: VIBROTACTILE FEEDBACK LIBRARY) vibration with a period which is inversely proportional to the vehicle speed. The vibration is mapped to the stick to the side to which the deviation occurs (i.e., overshooting the lane towards the right triggers the vibration in the right stick). This behavior can be toggled with behavior code 5 in the Toggle Haptics Message.

4.3.2.2.3 Light bars

Light feedback was prototyped in the form of two separate 360° light rings, one mounted around the wind shield and the other framing the secondary terminal display, provided by TTControl. The light ring is used to present information of the object detection feature. Detected objects within a customizable detection range will show up as a light signal as the section of the led-ring representing the angle of where the object is

currently detected. As an object changes its position the light signal reacts by changing color (if the object changes distance) and by changing position on the light ring (as the object moves along the machine).

4.3.2.2.4 Terminal display

Currently, the display lights up and shows the position of the snow groomer in a simulated environment, using this information to guide the operator home in case of e.g., a white out. The display will start up at the moment the snow groomer is started.

4.3.2.3 F13 - “Safe path home” guidance

The safe path home guidance makes use of a series of waypoints between the vehicle current position and the garage, computed on the vehicle and transmitted one at a time to the Haptics ECU. The haptic feedback is identical to the description provided for the Haptic track controls torque feedback for F12, in the case where only the next waypoint (with or without desired heading) is provided (i.e. not a lane-keeping function). From the haptics ECU perspective, this task is no different than conventional waypoint navigation as described above, hence no specific toggle is provided for this haptic behavior.

4.3.2.4 F14 - Inform operator about current blade settings and state, as well as discrepancies between them and optimal calculated blade settings

Summary

Partner	Output device	Displayed values	Mapping(s)
HAP	Haptic primary joystick force/torque feedback	Minimum distance between blade and ground	Unique mapping: Ground collision avoidance force feedback
HAP	Haptic primary joystick vibrotactile feedback	Blade axis end-stop	Unique mapping: End-stop vibrations
HAP	Haptic primary joystick vibrotactile feedback	Distance between blade and ground	Unique mapping: Ground collision warning

Table 15: F14 Feedback function summary table

4.3.2.4.1 Haptic primary joystick force/torque feedback

This function’s implementation depends on input kinematics for the blade. When using a standard 2DoF mapping, we only provide torque feedback around the x- and y- axes when controlling blade height and roll (button JJ2 pressed, see Figure 6). When using a 6DoF mapping, we only provide feedback when operating the joystick in “main blade” position, through force feedback on the z axis and torque feedback around the x axis.

Given a target blade height off the ground and the current blade height off the ground at both extremities of the blade, provided by the TTC control unit via a SENSOR DATA message, we compute feedback in a two-step process, only if part of the blade is below the set height limit (i.e. if the height at one extremity is lower than the prescribed minimum permissible height). First, if the blade is not parallel to the ground, torque feedback around the x-axis is provided to attempt to align the blade with the ground. Second, if the average height of the blade off the ground is below the set limit, we provide either torque feedback around the y-axis (standard input kinematics) or force feedback upward along the z-axis (6DoF input kinematics) computed using a PD controller used to convert the blade height error to a joystick deflection setpoint, towards which the joystick is pulled by per-axis virtual springs. This behavior can be toggled using behavior code 6

4.3.2.4.2 Haptic primary joystick vibrotactile ground collision warning

This function operates using the same input data as above provided by the TTC control unit. Below the preset threshold, the Haptics ECU triggers vibration pulses (OUT_OF_RANGE_L, see APPENDIX A: VIBROTACTILE

FEEDBACK LIBRARY) whose rate is inversely proportional to the penetration of the blade into the forbidden zone. This behavior can be toggled using behavior code 7.

4.3.2.4.3 Haptic primary joystick vibrotactile end-stop notification

The TTC CPU updates the Haptics ECU with the state of the blade relative to its end-stops on all 6 axes via the periodic Sensor Data message. When the Haptics ECU detects that any axis goes from a “not in end-stop” state to an “in end-stop” state, it triggers a one-off ENDSTOP vibration pattern (see APPENDIX A: VIBROTACTILE FEEDBACK LIBRARY). This behavior can be toggled using behavior code 8

4.3.2.5 F15 – Inform operator about recommended speed

Summary

Partner	Output device	Displayed values	Mapping(s)
HAP	Haptic track controls vibrotactile actuators	Recommended vehicle forward speed V_r based on e.g. slope incline, snow quality, proximity to obstacles etc.	(A) Excessive or insufficient speed warnings
HAP	Haptic track controls torque motors		(A) Hybrid heading/velocity PID controllers (B) Haptic brake assist

Table 16: F15 Feedback function summary table

4.3.2.5.1 Tactile feedback: Vibration in track control handles

On startup, the TTC control unit sends a Config message to the haptics ECU, which enables the track controls, followed by a Toggle Haptics message with behavior code 9 to toggle this behavior.

High-level control systems implemented in the TTC control unit provide the haptics ECU with a recommended speed in each SENSOR DATA message sent to the Haptics ECU, along with the current vehicle track speeds and vehicle forward velocity.

The haptics ECU compares the current vehicle forward velocity with the recommended velocity at all times. If the vehicle overshoots or undershoots the recommended velocity by more than 10%, OUT_OF_RANGE_L or OUT_OF_RANGE_H vibrations are respectively triggered with a period of 2s, alternating between the left and right levers. If the vehicle overshoots or undershoots the recommended velocity by more than 30%, the vibrations are switched to DANGER_OUT_OF_RANGE_L or DANGER_OUT_OF_RANGE_H respectively to indicate severe and potentially dangerous deviations. See APPENDIX A: VIBROTACTILE FEEDBACK LIBRARY for the full list of vibrotactile cues.

4.3.2.5.2 Force feedback: Resistive or assistive torque in track control levers

Mapping A: Hybrid heading/velocity PID controllers

High-level control systems implemented in the TTC control unit provide the haptics ECU with a recommended speed (and heading, see also Section 4.3.2.2.1) in each SENSOR DATA message sent to the haptics ECU. Specifically, the recommended velocity is compared against the vehicle velocity setpoint defined by the track control lever angles, yielding a vehicle velocity setpoint error ε_ω . Together with the vehicle heading setpoint error, this vehicle velocity setpoint error is translated to a pair of track velocity setpoint errors $\Delta\widehat{v}_L$ and $\Delta\widehat{v}_R$. Each of these track velocity setpoint errors is independently fed into a PID controller (“HapticsController” in Figure 12), yielding a torque applied to the respective control lever. In this manner, the operator is continuously nudged towards the lever position which would command the vehicle to advance at the desired velocity. This behavior can be toggled with behavior code 10.

Mapping B: Haptic brake assist

In the particular case where the situation calls for a target velocity of zero, we implement a haptic assistance for braking using torque feedback in the levers. This function is described below in Section 4.3.2.7.1.

4.3.2.6 F16 - Inform operator about current and target snow depth in front of the vehicle.

Summary

Partner	Output device	Displayed values	Mapping(s)
TUD	Projection	Snow depth	Projected cross section in defined distance to vehicle

Using a laser projector, a flipped cross section of the ground can be projected in front of the machine. However, this feedback is implemented on the mock-up cabin in the machine simulation and interaction Lab at TU Dresden (see also deliverable D5.6 “Multimodal Immersive Cockpit (final version)”).

4.3.2.7 F17 - Inform operator about the presence, distance to, and heading towards obstacles in the vicinity

Summary

Partner	Output device	Displayed values	Mapping(s)
HAP	Haptic track controls torque feedback	Distance to closest obstacle	Unique mapping
HAP	Haptic track controls vibrotactile feedback	Distance to closest obstacle	Unique mapping
TUD	Light bars	Detected object in vicinity, object relative heading, distance to object	Unique mapping

Table 17: F19 Feedback function summary table

4.3.2.7.1 Haptic brake assist (collision avoidance)

When the recommended velocity in a given direction is zero due to imminent collision with a detected obstacle or the detection of loss of traction (snow groomer digging itself into a pit), the lever applies maximum resistive torque τ_{max} (hardcoded in the haptics ECU) against said direction beyond the track controls' zero position. With the force feedback active, this entirely prevents the operator from driving the vehicle into the obstacle or continuing to dig themselves into a pit through loss of traction.

Internally, the haptics ECU defines a hardcoded minimum distance threshold $d_{min,obstacle}$ within which an obstacle is considered potentially risky. During operation, the TTC control unit continually supplies the haptics ECU with SENSOR DATA messages containing a list of detected obstacles sourced from any active obstacle detection system, in particular containing the heading $\theta_{obstacle}(i)$ and absolute distance $d_{obstacle}(i)$ to the obstacles.

From this, the haptics ECU selects only the subset of distances in the current forward direction of travel (none if the vehicle is immobile, all distances to obstacles for which $\theta_{obstacle}(i) \in [-90^\circ, 90^\circ]$ when travelling forward, or all distances for which $\theta_{obstacle}(i) \in [-180^\circ, -90^\circ] \cup [90^\circ, 180^\circ]$ when travelling backward).

If at any time it is determined that within this subset $d_{obstacle}(i) < d_{min,obstacle}$ the following torque is applied to the levers:

- If the lever angle > 0 and direction of the obstacle is forward, $-\tau_{max}$
- If the lever angle ≤ 0 and direction of the obstacle is forward, no torque
- If the lever angle < 0 and direction of the obstacle is backward, τ_{max}
- If the lever angle ≥ 0 and direction of the obstacle is backward, no torque

This behavior can be toggled with behavior code 11

4.3.2.7.2 Vibrotactile imminent collision warning

Similar to the function above, if at any time $d_{obstacle}(i) < d_{min,obstacle}$, the haptics ECU triggers periodic VIB_250 vibration pulses (see [APPENDIX A: VIBROTACTILE FEEDBACK LIBRARY](#)) with a period that varies inversely proportionally to the distance to the obstacle. This behavior can be toggled with behavior code 12

5 Use-case 2: Reachstacker

5.1 Simulation environments

Since use-case UC2 did not impose a specific prototype of a remote-control desk nor the use of a physical central vehicle controller such as in UC1, the implementation of the simulation environment was done using a set of physical UI elements arranged on a desktop which directly interface with a simulation PC.

5.1.1 Unity3D Simulation (VTT/HAP)

Figure 13: Interactions with the VTT/HAP simulators

The playable demonstration for the reachstacker use-case was developed under the heading of VTT, who built a virtual port environment featuring a virtual reachstacker vehicle model. Interaction with the simulation environment (viewing, provision of control commands) takes place using a set of physical controls (see Figure 13). The simulation display consists of three wall-sized screens, placed with an angle of 120° between each other. The total screen resolution available is 5760x1200 pixels. As input devices, the demo currently makes use of a Logitech Extreme 3D joystick for controlling the reachstacker's boom and spreader, and an Ultraleap Stereo IR 170 hand-tracking device for controlling the camera views and their position on the screen. A keyboard is also used for handling simulation aspects (such as changing the weather from rain to snow, etc.), and also for proving specific commands that were not bound to any of the other peripherals (such as disabling one or both of the AR load charts). The demo intentionally includes a high number of features available to the user, in order to understand which ones are felt to be the most useful and which ones are not really needed. All XR feedback functions except the haptics (i.e. visual and audio feedback within the simulated environment) are delivered entirely in simulation.

5.1.2 Virtual environment, vehicle simulation and sensor data simulation

The testing environment tries to resemble as much as possible a real working environment. Since reach stackers are used mostly in logistic hubs, a harbor asset was chosen (see Figure 14).

Figure 14: Simulated port for the UC2 demonstrator

The tasks focus on the control of boom and spreader (see Figure 15). The boom can be rotated upward or downward, and its telescopic arm can be extended or retracted. The spreader can be shifted to the left or right, and it can also be rotated clockwise and counterclockwise.

Figure 15: Simulated reachstacker boom and spreader DoF

Wind strength and direction are shown in the UI with a compass symbol that rotates to adjust to the direction the user is facing. Both direction and strength are constant, and they do not affect the simulation. They are meant to give an idea of what the user would see in a real scenario.

Data acquisition by the vehicle's virtual sensors is considered perfect, i.e. there is no measurement noise or uncertainty creating offsets between the "true" simulated data and the "sensed" simulated data. The simulated vehicle itself contains a virtual throttle sensor and IMU feeding back acceleration and orientation information. These sensors also behave in an ideal fashion. The simulated boom and spreader feature a virtual LIDAR sensor (see Figure 16). The LIDAR simulation consists in casting about 10000 rays every 0.3s from a specified position in the bottom part of the boom (where the real LIDAR could be placed), towards the front of the vehicle. Because of the resource-intensive task of ray casting in Unity, rays were shot precisely in the direction of one of the container's corners, with a total angle of 30° both for azimuth and zenith. If the user wants to visualize another angle, they can press the left and right arrow keys on the keyboard, so that the virtual camera is moved to the new corner, and the raycast is rotated towards the new corner's position. In a real environment, a normal LIDAR could possibly be capable of shooting rays on the whole container all the time, without the need to rotate it.

Figure 16: Simulated LIDAR

The spreader twistlocks contain virtual weight sensors which currently return the scripted weight and center of mass position of handled containers when the twist locks are engaged, once again behaving as ideal sensors. This allows the simulation to remain free of issues that would likely be introduced by a proper physics simulation, while providing essentially the same functionality when it comes to evaluating interactions.

5.1.2.1 Envisioned scenario tasks

The definitive sequence of scenario tasks will only be agreed upon once work from deliverable D3.2 has completed and both the scenarios and lists of component control and feedback functions reach their final state. However, VTT have prototyped a certain number of scenario events and functions in the context of user testing for the co-design process, which are reported in deliverables D3.4 "Low Fidelity Prototypes (first version)" and D4.4 "Interaction concepts (first version)".

5.1.3 Unity to Haption RaptorAPI software bridge

To allow effective haptic interaction with the Unity3D-based simulation running at 50Hz, it was required to design a custom software bridge internally running a 1kHz haptic rendering loop and interfacing with the 6DoF haptic arm via Haption’s commercially available RaptorAPI. This software runs as a background service, acting as a “Haptics Server” for a client implemented in Unity (see Figure 17). The communication between the Unity haptics client and the HapticServer is done via an on-machine TCP socket, similar to that implemented between the Haptics ECU and TTC CPU in the demonstrator for UC1 (see also deliverable D5.3 “Visualization and interaction infrastructure”).

Figure 17: "HapticServer" software bridge between Unity and the haptic device

In Unity, Haption furthermore designed a generic client allowing interaction with the HapticServer such that the device cartesian axis behaviors are entirely configurable and can be mapped to different inputs in the Unity simulation, and such that the various haptic feedback behaviors (force and tactile feedback) can be enabled, disabled and configured in a modular way.

5.1.4 Kalmar adapted training simulator

The target was to develop a simulator platform where Kalmar can further develop user experience for remote controlled and manually driven reachstackers. The first test cases were verifying if it is easier to utilize a steering wheel also when the operator is controlling the machine remotely. After this round the simulation environment was implemented with VTT’s environment. Second verification round was utilized to test in which use cases haptic control with joysticks gives best value. The third iteration round was related to audio signals and when they could be utilized so that they are helping operators without irritating them.

We implemented training simulator with the following features:

- Compact setup that does not require specific large room with wide doors etc.

- Moderate initial cost for Kalmar and later also for customers so that it is easier for them to buy as many simulators as they need.
- Platform is mainly aimed at basic testing and training but can be utilized for special training of experienced operators also with new UX features
- Including all new features of machines and control system
- Safe environment to test new features and technologies
- Portable if possible

We utilized following hardware and software components:

Simulator HW: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advantech IPC • Onboard PLC 	Simulator SW: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TwinCat • Codesys • NS • Onboard DAQ
RC Desk HW: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Liveview PC • RC Fleetview PC • Controls 	RC Desk SW: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RC Fleetview (Kalmar) • Visualization SW (Unity)
Kalmar server HW: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Server HW 	Kalmar server SW: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Application Key (Kalmar) • Scheduker (Kalmar) • RCC (Kalmar) • RC PLC DAQ (Kalmar) • Remote library (Kalmar) • Databases • Docker • VerneMQ • GOS

Table 18: Hardware and software components of Kalmar simulator

Figure 18: Kalmar testing/training simulator environment including machine specific controls

Figure 19: Transportation box for Kalmar simulator hardware

5.2 Control functions (input)

The analysis of the scenarios presented in Section 3.2 above yields the list of individual control functions summarized in Table 3. Below, we discuss the functions already implemented in part or in full in the state of the art, followed by a description of all proposed novel implementations.

5.2.1 State of the art

Figure 20: Reachstacker cabin

Currently, reachstacker cabins (see Figure 20) provide operators with key switches to start and stop the engine (C26) and execute hydraulic functions and various vehicle functions (C23, C25, C213). For driving functions, a steering wheel and pedals allow the operator to maneuver the vehicle (C28, C217). A joystick provides control over the hydraulics of the boom through joystick rotation (see Figure 21) and of the spreader through a set of four buttons, two for spreader shifting and two for spreader rotation. The twist-locks are actuated thanks to additional buttons on the joystick (C210, C211).

Figure 21: Reachstacker joystick input mapping

5.2.2 Control functions prototyped in simulation

This section presents the control functions prototyped in simulation for use-case UC2, following the same approach as that described in the introduction of Section 4.2.2 above.

5.2.2.1 C27 - Operator switches the machine to auto or RC mode

Summary

Partner	Input device	Controlled values	Mapping(s)
VTT	Keyboard	Machine operation mode (binary: auto or RC)	Unique mapping

Table 19: C27 Control function summary table

In the VTT simulation, the switch between auto and manual operation mode is scripted to follow the different stages of the simulation scenario. When prompted, the user provides confirmation by pressing “Enter” using the keyboard, indicating that the work is complete, at which point the simulator automatically switches to auto mode. The user is been instructed using text prompts in the UI.

5.2.2.2 C28 - Operator manually drives the machine

Summary

Partner	Input device	Controlled values	Mapping(s)
KAL	Steering wheel Gas pedal Machine specific controls (buttons, switches etc.)	Motor torque Front wheel orientation	Unique mapping

Table 20: C28 Control function summary table

The Kalmar simulation is the only one implementing manual driving (state-of-the-art) of the reachstacker. This is done in a state-of-the-art fashion, with gaming steering wheel and pedals, but other controls are from the real machine such as the selection of spreader length, twistlock controls etc. The control system is same as in real demonstration machine and it gets exactly the same signal as in a real machine.

5.2.2.3 C29 – Operator maneuvers boom and spreader

Summary

Partner	Input device	Controlled values	Mapping(s)
KAL	2DoF Joystick	Boom raising angle β	(A) Standard
VTT		Boom extension length L_B	
HAP	Primary haptic 6DoF Joystick	Spreader rotation angle θ Spreader lateral shift ΔS Spreader spread W_S	(A) Standard (B) 3 DoF Torque Joystick (C) 2-Rotation, 2-Translation Joystick (D) Direct control of container target pose

Table 21: C29 Control function summary table

5.2.2.3.1 2DoF Joystick Input

Both the VTT and Kalmar simulations include state-of-the-art 2-axis joystick manipulation. In the case of the VTT simulator, this is implemented using a commercially available ThrustMaster joystick with input axes and buttons handled by the Unity Input Manager system (see also Figure 28 below for details).

The Kalmar simulation uses state-of-the-art 2-axis joystick manipulation which can be replaced with a haptic joystick in the future. In the case of the Kalmar simulator, this is implemented using a commercially available joystick manufactured by Haptronics Oy with input axes and buttons handled by the Kalmar control system.

In both cases, the input mapping is exactly identical to that described in the state-of-the-art in Section 5.2.1.

5.2.2.3.2 6DoF Joystick Input

6DoF joystick input is specific to the Haption simulation. Figure 22 below shows the axis layout for the haptic manipulator and the effector (boom, spreader and twistlocks) in UC2. The manipulator provides 3 translational input axes (T_x , T_y , T_z) and three rotational input axes (R_x , R_y , R_z) as well as button inputs (binary states). The effector has 5 controllable axes which we will denote R1 through R5 as shown in Figure 22.

Figure 22: Manipulator and Effector axes in UC2.

In the following, we describe the different control mappings prototyped within the Haption simulation.

Mapping A: Standard – Description

This control function mapping replicates the original way in which a standard 2DoF Joystick controls a reachstacker’s spreader and boom. Ry controls R1, Rx controls R2, and button presses control the remaining axes (one pair of buttons for R3, one pair of buttons for R4 or R5, depending on whether the button presses are single long presses or double presses). The mode in which R5 is controlled (manual adjustment or cycling between preset spreader openings) must be configured beforehand. The large central button allows locking or unlocking of the twistlocks.

Figure 23: Button configuration for mapping A

Mapping B: 3 DoF Torque Joystick – Description

Based on Mapping A above, we add a rotational DoF around the manipulator z axis to control R3. Thus, the 3-position switch previously used to control R3 can now manually control R4, and the pair of lateral buttons controls R5. Single continuous presses control R5 in manual mode, while double presses cycle R5 between preset spreader openings. The large central button allows locking or unlocking of the twistlocks.

Figure 24: Button configuration for mapping B

Mapping C: 2-Rotation, 2-Translation Joystick – Description

In this mapping, both the translational and rotational degrees of freedom for the manipulator x and y axes are usable. Rotation around y controls the boom raising (R1), translation along the x axis controls boom extension (R2). Rotation around the x axis controls the spreader rotation (R3) and translation along the y axis controls the spreader shift (R4). The Joystick 3-position switch thus controls continuous adjustment to the spreader spread (R5), and the lateral buttons allow cycling towards the preset spreader widths (R5). As with all other mappings, the large central button allows locking or unlocking of the twistlocks.

Figure 25 Button configuration for mappings C and D

Mapping D: Direct control of the container target pose – Description

Figure 26: Mapping D – Direct control of the container target pose

This mapping significantly differs from the previous mappings. Indeed, instead of using the manipulator like a conventional joystick, where deviations from the zero position on an axis are translated into a velocity setpoint for the corresponding axis on the reachstacker, we make all three translational axes and the rotation around z available on the manipulator, which correspond to the actual degrees of freedom in which the container can be moved by the reachstacker. In this way, it becomes possible to directly control the container pose, using a set of fixed scaling factors and offsets between the manipulator pose in its own frame of reference and the container pose in the reachstacker frame of reference (see Figure 26).

Contrary to the other control mappings, this mapping requires a visual indication of the currently set container pose setpoint. Indeed, the manipulator dynamics do not correspond to the boom and spreader dynamics, which exhibit notable delays between receiving and reaching a positional or rotational setpoint. Therefore, we expect this mapping to only be effective when combined with e.g. an AR visualization of the target container pose. Such a visualization is implemented in the Haption simulation when input mapping D is selected, as shown in Figure 27 below.

Figure 27: AR visualization of the target container pose used with mapping (D)

The joystick buttons in this mapping are identical to that of mapping C above (see Figure 25), controlling only the spreader spread and twistlock locking and unlocking.

5.2.2.4 C210 – Operator engages/disengages the twistlocks

Summary

Partner	Input device	Controlled values	Mapping(s)
KAL	2DoF Joystick Button	Twistlock lock (binary: locked/unlocked)	Unique mapping
VTT			
HAP	Primary haptic 6DoF Joystick Button		

Table 22: C210 Control function summary table

In all simulator environments, the twistlock locking function is implemented as a state-of-the-art button press on the primary manipulator. VTT's simulator joystick mapping can be seen in Figure 28.

Figure 28: Joystick mapping introduction in help screen in VTT's simulator

The twistlock controls in the Kalmar simulation are described above in Section 5.2.2.3.1.

For the Haption simulation, see Section 5.2.2.3 above for the description of this interaction. For all simulations, see Section 5.2.2.5 below for a description of specifics of the automatic twistlock locking function.

5.2.2.5 C211 - Operator toggles the twistlock auto-lock functions

Summary

Partner	Input device	Controlled values	Mapping(s)
KAL	2DoF Joystick Button	Twistlock auto-lock (binary: enabled/disabled)	Unique mapping
VTT	None		N.A.
HAP	Keyboard		Unique mapping

Table 23: C211 Control function summary table

The KAL simulation includes a touchscreen toggle for the auto-lock function. The function is pre-activated in the VTT simulator as required by the interaction scenario script. In the Haption simulation, the auto-lock function can be toggled by pressing the Shift+A key combination on the keyboard, mimicking activation/deactivation that would occur using an in-vehicle touchscreen or button control.

5.2.2.6 C212 - Operator adjusts cabin camera position

Summary

Partner	Input device	Controlled values	Mapping(s)
VTT	Joystick side buttons	Cabin camera position on forward/backward axis	Unique mapping

Table 24: C212 Control function summary table

The cabin camera is fixed to the cabin location. In a real reach stacker, the user can move the cabin back and forth. In the VTT simulator, joystick buttons are used to move the cabin (see Figure 28).

5.2.2.7 C213 - Operator triggers emergency stop

Summary

Partner	Input device	Controlled values	Mapping(s)
KAL	Emergency Stop Button	Vehicle throttle	Unique mapping
VTT	Keyboard	All boom and spreader part velocities	Unique mapping
HAP	Primary 6DoF joystick deadman and emergency stop switch		Twistlock locking

Table 25: C213 Control function summary table

5.2.2.7.1 Emergency-stop button

The Kalmar simulator features a state-of-the-art emergency stop button on the operator control panel in the armrest (see Figure 18).

5.2.2.7.2 Keyboard-based emergency stop

The emergency stop feature is available to the operator as well – the vehicle can be immediately stopped by pressing the "Space" key. The emergency stop can be released with "Backspace", and to proceed to the next step of the scenario operator can press "Enter".

5.2.2.7.3 Haptic device emergency-stop and deadman switch

Because it poses unique risks associated to its force feedback capabilities, the primary haptic input device is equipped with both a dedicated emergency stop and a deadman switch in the device handle. If either of these is triggered (emergency stop pressed or deadman switch disengaged), not only are all force feedback functions put on standby, but also all reachstacker axis velocity or position change commands are immediately set to zero, freezing any movements of the effector. As such, triggering the haptic device's emergency stop button or disengaging its deadman switch by releasing the handle can act as a way for the operator to trigger a vehicle emergency stop. The hardware underlying these functions is described in more detail in deliverable D5.6 "Multimodal immersive cockpit (final version)".

5.2.2.8 C214 - Operator switches camera view

Summary

Partner	Input device	Controlled values	Mapping(s)
VTT	Leap motion camera	360° camera FoV angle and active camera (numbered 1 - 4).	Unique mapping

Table 26: C214 Control function summary table

In the VTT simulation, hand-tracking interactions were implemented as an alternative to mouse interaction with the cameras. The interactions are designed to be performed with the left hand, as the right hand is dedicated to handling the joystick. The user can pinch their thumb and index finger and then move their hand in any direction to make the camera rotate in the opposite direction, creating a “drag” effect that has the same effect as a mouse right-click-and-pan interaction. The user can also perform a “swipe” gesture to cycle the full-screen camera view to the previous camera or to the next camera. For this interaction, there is no direct mouse alternative; in that case, the user must click on one camera view to see its footage in full screen.

5.3 Modes of information presentation (feedback)

The analysis of the scenarios presented in Section 3.2.1 above yields the list of individual control functions summarized in Table 4. Below, we discuss the functions already implemented in part or in full in the state of the art, followed by a description of all proposed novel implementations.

5.3.1 State of the art

Reachstackers are conventionally equipped with a cabin providing clear visibility towards the front of the vehicle (F26, F211, F218, F221, F222, F223), along with rear-view mirrors and a rear-facing camera displaying its feed on an in-cabin monitor (F211, F217, F223, F231). Manipulation of containers is assessed directly visually by the operator, while contact with containers, the ground or trailers and successful locking is also assessed from auditory feedback from the environment (F212, F213, F214, F215, F216). Onboard monitoring and control units provide relevant functional, diagnostic and fault information about the vehicle to the operator via lights on the dashboard and an in-cabin display (F27, F28, F29, F210, F219, F228), usually over CAN (see Figure 20). Audio communication with service or harbor personnel takes place over in-cabin radio (F23).

5.3.2 Feedback functions prototyped in simulation

This section presents the control functions prototyped in simulation for use-case UC2, following the same approach as that described in the introduction of Section 4.3.2 above.

5.3.2.1 F25 - Inform operator of preset vehicle settings associated with operator ID, as well as their successful application

Summary

Partner	Output device	Displayed values	Mapping(s)
HAP	On-screen UI Primary 6DoF joystick	Haptic joystick per-axis preset spring stiffness and viscosity	Unique mapping

Table 27: F25 Feedback function summary table

This function was only partially prototyped with respect to the haptic device settings. In the Haption simulation, we prototyped a showcase of a customization screen for joystick mechanical properties via an on-screen UI, with the aim of understanding whether per-axis customization of joystick spring forces and viscosities could be of interest to operators. Figure 29 below shows the simulation screen UI for setting and applying custom joystick base mechanical properties, independently from the application input mapping.

Figure 29: UI of the "Joystick Configurator" simulator scene

5.3.2.2 F26 - Provide operator with clear view and earshot to machine operation and vicinity, through multiple camera views of vehicle

Summary

Partner	Output device	Displayed values	Mapping(s)
VTT	Screens for camera feeds Audio speakers	Environment camera views Environment audio	Unique mapping
KAL	Screens for camera feed Audio speakers		Unique mapping

Table 28: F26 Feedback function summary table

5.3.2.2.1 VTT Simulation multi-camera and environment audio feedback

The VTT simulation presents a set of four 360° cameras for the user to monitor, namely one front the operator’s cabin, one on the top of the spreader, one in the back of the vehicle for safety purposes, and a “drone view” camera (see Figure 30). The latter camera is more of an experimental one, and for the sake of feasibility can also represent a camera out of a light pole or in any other place of the logistic hub that provides a useful point of view of the reachstacker’s task. This view system is reused as is in the HAP simulation.

Figure 30: Available simulated camera views in the UC2 simulator

5.3.2.3 F27 - Inform operator of vehicle operational/faulty state

Summary

Partner	Output device	Displayed values	Mapping(s)
KAL	Terminal display	Vehicle faults	Unique mapping
HAP	Vibrotactile actuator in the joystick handle	Non-specific vehicle fault	Unique mapping

Table 29: F27 Feedback function summary table

5.3.2.3.1 KAL Simulation on-screen fault display

The KAL simulation features a visual display of faults on the screen.

5.3.2.3.2 HAP Simulation vibrotactile fault warning

The Haption simulation features a set of wizard-of-oz style toggles for triggering a vehicle faulty state (and associated haptic feedback), which when pressed again act as a keyboard trigger for bypassing the warning or notification when applicable. Table 30 below describes the vibrotactile warnings and their manual triggers and proposed meaning. See APPENDIX A: VIBROTACTILE FEEDBACK LIBRARY for the full list of vibrotactile cues.

Keyboard toggle	Example of Vehicle state	Vibration pattern	Expected operator reaction
Shift + 1	Dangerous vehicle fault, critical system has a major fault (e.g. flat tyre)	WARNING_UNSAFE	Do not start operation, fix issue immediately
Shift + 2	Vehicle operational, non-critical system has a minor fault or warning (e.g. windscreen wiper liquid getting low)	NOTIF_QUIET	Notification can be bypassed, fix issue as soon as practical
Shift + 3	Vehicle operational, non-critical system has a major fault (e.g. job system data transmission failure)	NOTIF_MED	Notification can be bypassed; operator should fix issue immediately if possible
Shift + 4	Vehicle operational, critical system warning or minor fault (e.g. oil level getting low)	NOTIF_LOUD	Notification cannot be bypassed; issue needs to be addressed immediately.

Table 30: Vibrotactile fault warnings in HAP simulation

5.3.2.4 F29 - Inform operator about list of assigned orders, pending jobs, job selection, job details and overview

Summary

Partner	Output device	Displayed values	Mapping(s)
KAL	Screen	Job information	Unique mapping

Table 31: F29 Feedback function summary table

The KAL simulation features a basic state-of-the-art job system with on-screen display

5.3.2.5 F210 - Provide operator with the layout or minimap of the port in the vicinity of the vehicle

Summary

Partner	Output device	Displayed values	Mapping(s)
KAL	Screen	Job target direction on minimap	Unique mapping

Table 32: F210 Feedback function summary table

The KAL simulation features a basic minimap indicating target direction on the screen

5.3.2.6 F211 - Alert operator to approaching machine

Summary

Partner	Output device	Displayed values	Mapping(s)
VTT	Camera streams (AR) Speakers	Detected obstacles	Unique mapping

Table 33: F211 Feedback function summary table

The VTT simulation provides AR highlights of obstacles and persons which are approaching machines in the camera feed. The obstacle tracking system emits emitting high-frequency beeping sound, which could be easily distinguished from the vehicle's backing sound. The beeping intervals are based on the distance to the obstacle and will become smaller as the obstacle gets closer. When an obstacle enters an imminent danger zone, the beeping is changed to a constant high-frequency tone.

5.3.2.7 F212 - Inform operator about safe space available for extending the spreader

Summary

Partner	Output device	Displayed values	Mapping(s)
VTT	AR Load Chart	Admissible container positions based on weight	Unique mapping
HAP	Vibrotactile	Spreader safe extension limits and imminent collision	Unique mapping
HAP	Force feedback	Spreader safe extension limits and imminent collision	Unique mapping

Table 34: F212 Feedback function summary table

5.3.2.7.1 VTT Simulation AR Load Chart

The AR guidance system's load chart displays the left side of the load chart by default, with an option for users to switch each side on and off. An overload indicator was added to link the load chart to a visualization of the tipping axis. The indicator appears in the center of the screen when the container nears the tipping distance (tipping axis shown in yellow), and an audio alert sounds when the container reaches the tipping distance (tipping axis shown in red). See Figure 31.

Figure 31: Example of AR based load chart which is supporting operator during pick and placing task

5.3.2.7.2 HAP Simulation spreader safe extension limit feedback

In the Haption simulation, we propose a set of feedback components for intuitive avoidance of collisions during spreader or container motion. The exact axes concerned with this force feedback and its computation depend on the input mapping:

a/ Mappings A (standard 2 axis joystick), B (3-axis joystick) and C (4DoF joystick)

Safe extension limits are computed on a per-axis basis, based on the current direction of travel of the spreader (or transported container). In the current direction of travel, we evaluate the bounding volume encompassing all possible future poses of the spreader and/or container to determine whether obstacles are found within this volume. If this is the case, we determine the shortest travel distance before the first potential collision, and re-project this on the actuated boom and spreader axes in order to obtain per-axis travel limits (see Figure 32).

Figure 32: Sensing safe spreader extension limit in the HAP simulation.

The feedback of this per-axis distance to closest collision is always based on the same virtual force calculation presented in Figure 33. The computed virtual forces are then transformed into per-axis forces or torques on the manipulator using per-axis gains, depending on the input mapping (see Section 5.2.2.3). We propose two options with slightly different implications regarding the admissible positions of the axes and the way resistive forces are felt: Spring-based collision avoidance and damping-based collision avoidance. Both these approaches are based on the definition of a threshold distance d_{thresh} below which a collision is considered imminent.

In the spring-based collision avoidance scenario, a virtual force acting on the container is always computed as long as the container is within said threshold distance from the obstacle, with a magnitude that is proportional to the penetration beyond the threshold. This has the effect of generating a permanent force or torque at the manipulator, prompting the operator to pull the spreader or container back towards the threshold. This makes this form of feedback potentially less practical in the event of signaling collisions with surfaces on which the spreader or container must come into contact (e.g. container top surface, other containers in stack, ground or truck bed).

In the damping-based collision avoidance scenario, a virtual force acting on the container is computed proportional to the penetration velocity of the container beyond the threshold. This has the effect of countering any attempted further motion towards the obstacle with a resistive force or torque, without pushing the manipulator handle to guide the spreader or container back towards the threshold.

Figure 33: Virtual force calculation for the collision avoidance feedback

In mapping A, only R1 and R2 are actuated with the joystick Rx and Ry axes, it is therefore the most sensible to apply torque feedback to both these axes. For the remaining axes, we propose to rely solely on the vibrotactile feedback provided in parallel (axis-independent). The implemented vibrotactile feedback is a vibration pulse train with varying pulse rate, inversely proportional to the penetration within the threshold. We implement this by dividing the threshold distance into ten equal-length segments, each of which are mapped to the generation of a PULSE_T1 to PULSE_T10 periodic vibrotactile cue (see [APPENDIX A: VIBROTACTILE FEEDBACK LIBRARY](#)).

Mapping B is mostly identical to mapping A, except that we also apply a resistive torque on the manipulator vertical rotation axis controlling R3. Note that we recalculate the distance to collision on the fly at every frame, therefore we can easily update the remaining admissible extension on R2 and rotations on R1 or R3 before collision, and independently calculate resistive torques for each of the joystick axes. Vibrotactile feedback is provided identically to mapping A above.

In Mapping C, torque feedback is still applied on the joystick Ry (R1) and Rx (R4) axes, along with force feedback on the Tx (R2) and Ty (R3) axes. Vibrotactile feedback is provided identically to mapping A above.

For all three mappings, potential collisions during spreader extension are determined as described above for the other axes. If one is to occur, the spreader extension action is not performed and the operator is notified with a FAILURE vibration (see [APPENDIX A: VIBROTACTILE FEEDBACK LIBRARY](#)).

b/ Mapping D: Direct position control

Here we rely on Unity physics to detect collisions between the controlled container pose setpoint and objects of the environment. When these occur, the container setpoint is blocked by the physics collision and feeds back information on the collision point and normal. These allow us to implement a temporary planar haptic constraint, prevent further translation along the negative of the normal, as well as any rotations around the haptic plane's axes. Since the container setpoint dictates the future pose of the actual container, this implicitly limits motions of the container to the space within which no collisions with the environment can occur.

We determine potential collisions around the container setpoint using an additional bounding volume used to compute a distance d to close obstacles. Based on this distance d , we trigger vibrotactile feedback identically to that described for mapping A through C.

Figure 34: Vibrotactile feedback of potential collisions based on the container setpoint position

For the spreader extension, we determine potential collisions similarly to the procedure described for mapping A through C above, and if one would occur, the action is not performed and the operator is notified with a FAILURE vibration (see APPENDIX A: VIBROTACTILE FEEDBACK LIBRARY).

5.3.2.8 F214 - Inform operator about horizontal and vertical distance between twist locks and container corners

Summary

Partner	Output device	Displayed values	Mapping(s)
VTT	Color-coded AR distance lines	Distance and direction from twistlocks to corresponding container corners	Unique mapping
HAP	Vibrotactile	Distance between spreader and container top.	Unique mapping
HAP	Force feedback	Direction of motion for spreader to come into contact.	Unique mapping

Table 35: F214 Feedback function summary table

5.3.2.8.1 AR Twistlock « laser » lines

The VTT simulation introduced color-coded distance lines that connected the container's casting corners to the reachstacker's twist locks to provide visual hints even in the front camera (the previous hints were only visible from the spreader camera) as could be seen Figure 28. This feature was motivated by the fact that especially experienced drivers tend to rely mostly on the front camera, and they were thus missing a lot of the AR information that was more visible on other cameras. Traditional traffic lights were added to the spreader, as well as spreader width presents for each container size (for 20, 30, and 40 ft containers).

Figure 35: Color-coded distance lines

5.3.2.8.2 HAP Simulation tactile distance feedback

The vibrotactile feedback implemented for rendering imminent collisions (see Section 5.3.2.7 above) can be used as-is for rendering the distance between the twistlocks and container corners.

5.3.2.8.3 HAP Simulation spreader placement force feedback guides

The Haption simulation implements what we refer to as force-feedback “funnel” guides to help the operator to place the spreader in the ideal position above a container to be lifted, or a container in the ideal position above where it must be placed. These guides are different depending on the input kinematics, but always provide an implicit representation of the remaining distance between the spreader and target container which complements the explicit visual and vibrotactile feedback of the distance.

a/ Mappings A, B and C (2DoF, 3DoF, 4DoF Input mappings)

Given a known target pose for the spreader (twistlocks aligned with all container corners, vertically offset by 30cm) and a given current spreader pose, we determine a sequence of required motions, proceeding in order through all boom and spreader axes (R1 through to R5, see Figure 22). In turn for each axis where a motion is required, if that axis is actuated by a motion of the joystick, we apply forces on this axis guiding the operator towards the joystick axis position required to bring the boom/spreader axis into the desired position. The joystick deflection error is derived from the axis position error using a simple PID controller. Finally, we apply a spring force on the joystick axis to pull the handle towards the computed ideal joystick axis pose (see Table 36 for a pseudocode summary of the algorithm employed).

<pre> For axis Rx in R1:R4: if (Rx is actuated by joystick axis Jy) && while ($e_{Rx} > threshold$): Compute reachstacker axis position error: $e_{Rx} = Rx_{current\ position} - Rx_{target\ position}$; Compute corresponding joystick deflection error: $e_{Jy} = PID(e_{Rx})$; Saturate joystick deflection: if $e_{Jy} > maximum_deflection_{Jy}$: $e_{Jy} = maximum_deflection_{Jy}$; else if $e_{Jy} < -1 * maximum_deflection_{Jy}$: $e_{Jy} = -1 * maximum_deflection_{Jy}$; end if; Apply spring force towards ideal joystick deflection on the axis: $F_{Jy} = K_{axis} * e_{Jy}$; end if; end for; </pre>
--

Table 36: Pseudo-code algorithm for haptic "funnel" guides (for input mappings A, B and C)

Finally, once the target position above the container is reached and the operator has manually set the correct spreader opening based on visual and vibration feedback, a final downward spring force on the joystick axis actuating R1 is generated in the same way as described above, to bring the spreader in perfect contact with the container.

b/ Mapping D (4DoF Direct position control of the container pose setpoint)

For this mapping, guidance is much simpler since the operator is directly controlling the container pose setpoint. The same target pose offset vertically from the target container by 30cm is computed and used as the target pose for a set of translational and rotational springs pulling the haptic manipulator handle pose towards the target pose. Once this pose is reached and the operator has manually set the correct spreader opening based on visual and vibration feedback, a final downward spring force on the joystick axis actuating R1 is generated in the same way as described above.

5.3.2.9 F215 - Inform operator that twistlocks can be safely engaged/disengaged

Summary

Partner	Output device	Displayed values	Mapping(s)
VTT / KAL	"Traffic-light" visual indicator	Proximity of twistlocks to container corners	Unique mapping
HAP	Vibrotactile	Availability of twistlock locking	Unique mapping
HAP	Force feedback	Spreader collision force feedback	Unique mapping

Table 37: F215 Feedback function summary table

5.3.2.9.1 Traffic-light indicators

All simulations feature state-of-the-art visual feedback through "traffic light" indicators on the spreader (see Figure 36). A red light indicates that the twistlocks are out of range, an orange light indicates proximity to a safe position for engaging or disengaging, and a green light indicates that the twistlocks can be safely engaged or disengaged, depending on whether a container is currently being carried or not.

Figure 36: Example of traffic light indicator in VTT's simulator

5.3.2.9.2 Haptic ground collision indications

The HAP simulation provides haptic collision feedback for ground or container contact and tactile indications for function availability. This is a simple horizontal planar haptic constraint, reprojected on the relevant joystick axes depending on the mapping (see **Error! Reference source not found.**), preventing any further motion into beyond the plane in case of direct position control (mapping D), or beyond the axis zero position on the lifting and lowering axis in case of position-velocity control (mappings A, B and C).

5.3.2.9.3 Tactile locking/unlocking function availability notification

A set of vibration cues is defined to indicate the availability of the twistlock locking or unlocking functions (or lack thereof). Whenever the operator transitions between a spreader or container pose in which locking or unlocking is not possible towards one where locking or unlocking is possible (or vice-versa), the Haptics ECU triggers a NOTIF_MED vibration (see APPENDIX A: VIBROTACTILE FEEDBACK LIBRARY).

When the operator successfully executes a locking or unlocking action, the Haptics ECU respectively triggers a LOCK_CLOSE or LOCK_OPEN vibration.

If an attempt to lock or unlock is made outside of a zone where this is possible, the action is not executed and the Haptics ECU triggers a FAILURE vibration pattern.

5.3.2.10 F216 - Inform operator that twist locks have successfully been engaged/disengaged

Summary

Partner	Output device	Displayed values	Mapping(s)
VTT / KAL	Traffic light indicator	Twistlock locking/unlocking possible or not	Unique mapping
VTT	AR overlays	Container transported/not transported	Unique mapping
HAP	Vibrotactile	Locking/unlocking success or failure	Unique mapping
HAP	Force feedback	Transported weight	Unique mapping

Table 38: F216 Feedback function summary table

5.3.2.10.1 Traffic light indicators

All simulations feature state-of-the-art visual feedback through “traffic light” indicators on the spreader as previously described in Section 5.3.2.9.1.

5.3.2.10.2 Implicit feedback through AR overlay toggles

The VTT simulation additionally provides implicit feedback through the automatic activation and deactivation of AR overlays described e.g. in Section 5.3.2.7.1 or 5.3.2.8.1.

5.3.2.10.3 Tactile locking/unlocking indication

This function is described above in Section 5.3.2.9.3.

5.3.2.10.4 Container weight force feedback

When a container is first gripped by the spreader, we apply force feedback to give an indication of the transported mass to the operator. This force feedback is then removed when the container is released, thus providing implicit indications of successful locking or unlocking of the twistlocks. The force feedback for the container mass is described in detail in Section 5.3.2.21.

5.3.2.11 F218 - Inform operator that boom and spreader are in a suitable position for driving / transport.

Summary

Partner	Output device	Displayed values	Mapping(s)
VTT	AR load chart	Admissible container positions based on weight	Unique mapping

Table 39: F218 Feedback function summary table

The VTT simulation features the AR load chart showing suitable transport positions, which is described in Section 5.3.2.7 above.

5.3.2.12 F221 - Inform operator that container has been sufficiently lowered to allow release.

Summary

Partner	Output device	Displayed values	Mapping(s)
HAP	Vibrotactile actuator in 6DoF joystick handle	Ground contact (binary: not in contact/in contact)	Unique mapping

HAP	6DoF Joystick		Unique mapping
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Table 40: F221 Feedback function summary table

We assume the vehicle computer can infer the current distance between the bottom of the container and the ground. This could be thanks to LIDAR on the boom, image processing from the front-facing camera views and/or the known boom and spreader kinematics and container dimensions.

Once the distance between the container and the ground goes below a preset threshold (e.g. 25mm), the system assumes there is contact between the container and the ground, triggering the haptic feedback components that are enabled.

5.3.2.12.1 Vibrotactile ground collision feedback

When the container is considered as coming into contact with the ground, we trigger an IMPACT vibration cue (see [APPENDIX A: VIBROTACTILE FEEDBACK LIBRARY](#)).

5.3.2.12.2 Ground collision force feedback

We implement a planar haptic constraint on the handle reprojected on the joystick axis actuating R1 for input kinematic mappings A, B or C (or not reprojected in case of input kinematic mapping D). This yields a maximum resistive force or torque preventing further lowering, depending on the input mapping.

5.3.2.13 F222 - Inform operator that spreader has cleared the container.

Summary

Partner	Output device	Displayed values	Mapping(s)
HAP	Vibrotactile handle	Spreader has cleared the container	Unique mapping
HAP	Force feedback joystick		Unique mapping

Table 41: F222 Feedback function summary table

The Haption simulation provides haptic constraints on movement while spreader has not cleared the container as well as vibrotactile feedback to notify that the spreader has indeed cleared the container. Both these functions rely on detection that a container needs to be cleared, based on the fact that the twistlocks have been successfully released. Once this happens, the current spreader height is compared against a “safe” position determined at a set vertical threshold above the recently released container.

5.3.2.13.1 Vibrotactile notifications for container clearing

When the height of the spreader is detected to be going above the set vertical threshold, we trigger a NOTIF_MED vibrotactile cue to give the operator an unobtrusive notification indicating that other spreader motions are now probably safe.

5.3.2.13.2 Haptic handrail constraint for container clearing

To assist the operator in safely clearing a released container, we implement a “haptic handrail” constraint by locking all axes other than that actuating R1 upward (upward motion of the spreader) until the set vertical offset of the spreader from the container is achieved. The trigger for this assistive function is the detection that a released container needs to be cleared, which is simply inferred from the fact that the container was previously successfully released from the spreader.

For input kinematic mappings A, B and C, when we detect that a container needs to be cleared, the joystick is first instantly forced back to the neutral position, after which only the joystick rotation or translation allowing upward motion along R1 is released. We track the distance between the spreader and top of the container, and allow velocities in both directions along R1 as long as this distance is above a minimum

threshold. Once the clearing threshold has been reached, all input axes are released again, providing full control of the spreader to the operator.

For input kinematic mapping D, we also constrain the motion of the spreader pose setpoint to the vertical translation axis above the container in a similar manner. Once the clearing threshold has been reached by the actual spreader pose, we then release all joystick handle DoF to return full control of the spreader pose setpoint to the operator.

5.3.2.14 F223 - Inform operator of the presence of persons in the vicinity of the vehicle

Summary

Partner	Output device	Displayed values	Mapping(s)
VTT	Camera feed (AR)	Presence & location of persons	Unique mapping

Table 42: F223 Feedback function summary table

The VTT simulation provides AR highlights of persons in the camera feed, person has YOLO type of boundary box around the tracked person, see Figure 37.

Figure 37: Example of person tracking and highlighting in VTT's simulator

5.3.2.15 F224 - Inform operator that spreader has reached an end-stop or target position.

Summary

Partner	Output device	Displayed values	Mapping(s)
HAP	Vibrotactile	Axis endstop reached	Unique mapping
HAP	Force feedback	Force feedback "funnel" guidance	Unique mapping
HAP	Force feedback	Force feedback of axis endstops	Unique mapping

Table 43: F224 Feedback function summary table

5.3.2.15.1 Vibrotactile end-stops

Independent of input kinematics, we provide vibrotactile feedback to indicate that axis end-stops have been reached. When an axis is driven into an endstop, we trigger an ENDSTOP vibration (see APPENDIX A: VIBROTACTILE FEEDBACK LIBRARY).

5.3.2.15.2 Force feedback "funnel" guidance

The force-feedback "funnel" guides described above in Section 5.3.2.8.3 also provide an implicit indication that a target position has been reached by the spreader.

5.3.2.15.3 Force-feedback of axis endstops

For input mapping A, B and C, we provide force feedback of detected reach stacker axis endstops by locking the relevant joystick DoF in the direction of the endstop using virtual stiff springs.

5.3.2.16 F225 – Inform operator that the job is complete

Summary

Partner	Output device	Displayed values	Mapping(s)
KAL	Screen	Job information	Unique mapping

Table 44: F225 Feedback function summary table

The KAL simulation provides visual feedback that the job is complete in the job system UI (see also Section 5.3.2.4).

5.3.2.17 F228 - Provide dashboard of the vehicle's parameters

Summary

Partner	Output device	Displayed values	Mapping(s)
KAL	Screen	Vehicle functional parameters	Unique mapping

Table 45: F228 Feedback function summary table

The KAL simulation features state-of-the-art on-screen display of vehicle parameters (fuel, oil temperature, gearbox temperature).

5.3.2.18 F229 - Inform operator about distance and ideal route to target location.

Summary

Partner	Output device	Displayed values	Mapping(s)
VTT	AR overlays	Vehicle path Front wheels' orientation	Unique mapping
KAL	On-screen minimap	Distance to and location of job target	Unique mapping

Table 46: F229 Feedback function summary table

5.3.2.18.1 Path and distance AR display

The AR guidance system of the VTT's simulator includes wheel direction visualization (Figure 38). This feature together with path visualization will enhance operator awareness of the self-driving vehicle movement direction.

Figure 38: Self-driving vehicle's path and wheel direction visualization.

5.3.2.18.2 Minimap

The KAL simulation features a basic minimap which provides information on the location and distance to the job target.

5.3.2.19 F230 - Inform operator about current auto driving functions being executed

Summary

Partner	Output device	Displayed values	Mapping(s)
VTT	AR overlays	Front wheels' orientation	Unique mapping

Table 47: F230 Feedback function summary table

The VTT simulation provides an AR overlay of the wheel angles seen “through the chassis”, which enhance operator awareness of the self-driving vehicle movement direction (See Figure 38).

5.3.2.20 F231 - Inform operator about relative position of objects, persons, vehicles or targets in the environment.

Summary

Partner	Output device	Displayed values	Mapping(s)
VTT	AR overlays	Locations and dimensions of targets, obstacles, persons or vehicles	Unique mapping

Table 48: F231 Feedback function summary table

The VTT simulation provides object, person and vehicle highlights in the camera feed, as well as highlights of target containers and trucks. Examples can be seen in Figure 39.

Figure 39: Example of the container and person highlighting in the VTT's simulator.

5.3.2.21 F232 - Inform operator about container weight and/or center of mass.

Summary

Partner	Output device	Displayed values	Mapping(s)
VTT	AR visual overlays	Container center of mass ground projection Vehicle and container center plane (w. respect to mass distribution)	Unique mapping
HAP	Force feedback	Transported container mass	Unique mapping
HAP	Force feedback	Container center of mass imbalance (for input mapping C)	Unique mapping
HAP	Vibration feedback	Container center of mass imbalance	Unique mapping

Table 49: F232 Feedback function summary table

5.3.2.21.1 AR weight and COM overlay

The VTT simulation provides AR visual overlays of container weight distribution and center of mass (See example in Figure 41).

Figure 40: Example of simulation provides AR visual overlays of container weight distribution and center of mass in the VTT's simulator.

5.3.2.21.2 Transported container mass force feedback

Experiments with constant forces or torques applied to the joystick axis actuating R1 (lifting/lowering) used to render container weight led us to conclude that such feedback is not optimal in terms of ease of manipulation and safety, as the operator needs to actively counter the rendered forces to keep a manipulated container at the desired height. Rater, we determined that applying viscous friction or additional spring forces to the joystick which are proportional to the container weight could give an understandable impression of manipulated container weight without impeding manipulation.

These resistive forces are isotropic across all manipulator axes (as defined based on the input kinematics). For input mappings A, B and C, the haptic joystick implements position-velocity control for the spreader. Thus, layering an additional spring force pulling the manipulator towards zero on all axes based on the container weight is equivalent to a virtual viscous force acting on the manipulated container. We calculate these forces and torques as follows for a given joystick axis x :

$$\begin{aligned}\vec{F}_x &= -k_T(m) * \vec{d}_x = -k_T(m) * K_x * \vec{v}_x \\ \vec{\tau}_x &= -k_R(m) * \vec{\theta}_x = -k_R(m) * K_x * \vec{\omega}_x\end{aligned}$$

Where F_x and τ_x are the force or torque applied to the manipulator along an axis x , $k_T(m)$ and $k_R(m)$ is the defined spring stiffness coefficients for translation and rotation which depend on the container mass m , and d_x and θ_x are the joystick linear or angular deflections along the axis x . The deflections relate to the velocity setpoints \vec{v}_x and $\vec{\omega}_x$ thanks to the per-axis control gain K_x , which highlights how these spring forces are in fact equivalent to viscous friction applied to the manipulated container.

For input mapping D, the haptic joystick implements position-position control for the container. Thus, adding viscosity to the manipulation based on the container mass is very straightforward, and done as follows for any axis x :

$$\vec{F}_x = -v_T(m) * \vec{v}_x \text{ and } \vec{\tau}_x = -v_R(m) * \vec{\omega}_x$$

Where F_x and τ_x are the force or torque applied to the manipulator along an axis x , $v_T(m)$ and $v_R(m)$ is the defined viscous friction coefficients for translation and rotation which depend on the container mass m , and v_x and ω_x are the translational or rotational container velocities along the axis x .

5.3.2.21.3 Force feedback COM adjustment guidance (Mapping C)

Haption considered the implementation of a force feedback rendering of container imbalance for mapping C (mappings A and B do not actuate the spreader shift using a joystick axis, and mapping D already allows highly intuitive centering of the container load using the AR overlays, making further rendering unnecessary). However, early prototypes quickly highlighted a major design issue in the context of THEIA^{XR}: Force must be displayed on the haptic device axis actuating R4 for feedback of the container imbalance to be understandable. However, displaying this force to show an existing imbalance (i.e., force moving the axis off center) causes the system to autonomously push the container out of balance unless the operator reacts rapidly to counter said force. This poses an obvious safety risk which appears incompatible with the objectives of the THEIA^{XR} project.

One envisioned solution to this problem was to provide two modes of operation for the primary haptic joystick, the first being a “control” mode allowing the operator to move the container without feeling the imbalance, and the second being a “perception” mode allowing the operator to feel the imbalance without any joystick motions moving the spreader. By switching back and forth between modes, an operator could precisely know of any imbalance, then adjust the load without any added risk being introduced by the system’s behavior. However, this iterative back-and-forth switching between modes appears time consuming and not very ergonomic, which once again goes against the objectives of the THEIA^{XR} project.

Therefore, the only solution which appears possibly beneficial is to implement force feedback pulling the operator towards the spreader shift position which would place the container in balance, i.e. a form of corrective guidance for the spreader shift. We achieve this by calculating the spreader shift position error which would bring the container in balance $\varepsilon_{x\ shift}$. Using a PID controller taking this error as input, we derive a desired spreader shift velocity $\widehat{v_{shift}}$. Given a current spreader shift velocity v_{shift} , we can compute a spreader shift velocity error:

$$\varepsilon_{v\ shift} = \widehat{v_{shift}} - v_{shift}$$

Applying a proportional gain to this error, we compute a spring force to the spreader shift axis (joystick translation Ty) which pulls the handle towards the desired shift velocity.

5.3.2.21.4 Tactile COM adjustment guidance (all mappings)

For all input kinematics, we propose tactile assistance to container COM adjustment. For this, we calculate the spreader shift position error which would bring the container in balance $\varepsilon_{x\ shift}$. Based on the magnitude of this error and the direction in which the corrective motion should occur, we provide vibrotactile feedback cues as shown in Table 50 (see APPENDIX A: VIBROTACTILE FEEDBACK LIBRARY for the list of cues):

Magnitude of $\varepsilon_{x\ shift}$	Corrective motion to the left	Corrective motion to the right
$\varepsilon_{x\ shift} \leq 10cm$ (deadband)	none	none
$10cm < \varepsilon_{x\ shift} \leq 40cm$	OUT_OF_RANGE_H	OUT_OF_RANGE_L
$40cm < \varepsilon_{x\ shift}$	DANGER_OUT_OF_RANGE_H	DANGER_OUT_OF_RANGE_L

Table 50: Vibrotactile cues based on container COM imbalance

5.3.2.22 F233 - Project the container limits or ideal loading position on the ground

Summary

Partner	Output device	Displayed values	Mapping(s)
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VTT	AR overlays	Container corners ground projection	Unique mapping
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Table 51: F233 Feedback function summary table

AR guidance can be utilized for loading containers onto trailers or on the ground. These AR hints include corner projections on the ground, providing precise placement guidance. Additionally, the container's mass distribution is illustrated, offering valuable insight into the weight and balance, ensuring a more efficient and safe loading process (Figure 41).

Figure 41: Example of the corner projections on the ground, providing precise placement guidance.

6 Use-case 3: Excavator

6.1 Simulation environment

The playable demonstration for the excavator use-case uses a pair of simulated environments developed by TUD and Creanex respectively, which interface with the physical control and feedback elements installed in the mock-up cabin built at TUD (described in detail in deliverable D5.6 “*Multimodal Immersive Cockpit (final version)*”).

The excavator simulator is based on the Creanex simulation platform. The working environment is an artificial construction site (see Figure 42) with which the virtual excavator interacts. Joysticks and pedal inputs are converted to virtual joint torques which move the machine parts. Counter forces are computed on the contact points between excavator and environment and also have an effect on the movement of the virtual machine parts. The ground surface of the working area is modelled by a dense triangular mesh, whose shape can be updated in real-time to visualize the excavation of holes and ditches.

Figure 42: Excavator in simulated environment

The top-level architecture of the Creanex simulator platform is presented in Figure 5 of Section 4.1. The Creanex simulation platform and available features for sensor simulations and other capabilities are presented in deliverable D4.5 “*Concept of virtual user interface (first version)*”.

6.2 Control functions (input)

The analysis of the vision scenarios presented in Section 3.3.1 above yields the list of individual control functions in Table 5.

6.2.1 State of the art

Conventional excavators use a combination of joysticks, pedals, a steering wheel, keypads and other physical control elements to control the several functions of the machine. Keypads, or in more modern vehicles, small touch displays, are used to set up the machine (starting, control of power distribution, control of the support beams, switching modes etc.) (C31).

If the machine is set up for driving, pedals and a steering wheel are used to control direction and speed (C32). Additionally, a parking brake and slewing brake are used to stop the tracks and carriage rotation.

Excavators can be used with a variety of tools (e.g., buckets of different shapes and sizes, grippers, hydraulic hammers, shaker, and many more) that require unique control features. As the analog buttons of excavators must cover all these functionalities, a lot of space is used to accommodate them, usually in the right armrest. In work mode, two joysticks are used to control the four degrees of freedom of the tool (tool angle, arm angle, boom angle, and carriage rotation) as per the control pattern in use on the vehicle (see Figure 43). Joystick rotation angles map to rotation velocity around the controlled degree of freedom (C33).

Figure 43: Two most common excavator joystick control patterns²

Some excavators have even more degrees of movement that are often mapped on thumb-joysticks or switches mounted on the joysticks. Regarding the tool control, excavators have safety features that are implemented to prevent mishandling. The most prominent function is a lever mounted on the left armrest that has to be brought into working position, connecting the joysticks to the control circuit to make them effective.

6.2.2 Envisioned control functions

This section presents the control functions prototyped in simulation for use-case UC3, following the same approach as that described in the introduction of Section 2.

6.2.2.1 C31 - Operator starts the engine, powers down the vehicle, or locks all moving parts

Summary

Partner	Input device	Controlled values	Mapping(s)
TUD	physical buttons placed in the TUD mock-up cabin directly interfaced to CREA sim (see deliverable D5.6 "Multimodal Immersive Cockpit (final version)")	Engine start/stop (binary) Moving parts locked/unlocked (binary)	Unique mapping

Table 52: C31 Control function summary table

Real cabins of construction machines feature a safety lever which locks all movements of the machine. In the mockup, a simple push-button is used to switch the machine on and to enable machine movements.

² Figure adapted from Proctor et al., 2022 [2]

6.2.2.2 C32 - Operator drives and orients the excavator

Summary

Partner	Input device	Controlled values	Mapping(s)
TUD	Physical steering wheel and pedals in the TUD mock-up cabin	Steering and Driving (backwards/forwards)	Unique mapping

Table 53: C32 Control function summary table

The state-of-the-art in steering and driving an excavator is either a steering wheel and pedals for wheeled machines or levers/pedals for tracked machines. In some machines, especially in wheel loaders, a steering and driving functionality is possible with the joysticks as well. This is used as an alternative control concept.

6.2.2.3 C33 - Operator controls drive, carriage, boom, arm and bucket to maneuver on site and effect surface profile

Summary

Partner	Input device	Controlled values	Mapping(s)
TUD	TUD cabin pair of joysticks (CAN)	slewing, boom movement, arm movement, bucket movement	Unique mapping

Table 54: C33 Control function summary table

The main working movements are performed with the two joysticks. Using industrial joysticks from real machines give the operator the correct ergonomic and resistance to emulate the real machine environment, see Figure 46.

Figure 44: Mobile Simulator with industrial joysticks to control the excavator simulation

6.2.2.4 C34 - Operator calls up a visualization of the planned excavation on screen and manipulates view angle and data augmentation in the visualization to familiarity with the task

Summary

Partner	Input device	Controlled values	Mapping(s)
TUD	Off-the-shelf touchscreen	Main GUI navigation, button press, 3D-view manipulation	Unique mapping

Table 55: C34 Control function summary table

Touch screens are the state-of-the-art solution for the main source of information about the machine state. They usually display simple scalar information in dashboards and allow inputs via touch buttons. In this GUI, a strong focus lies on the 3D-scene visualization. Hence, multitouch gestures are more important to control the 3D-scene view.

6.2.2.5 C35 - Operator manipulates CAD-model of planned pit to fit local requirements in advance to starting the mission

Summary

Partner	Input device	Controlled values	Mapping(s)
TUD	Touchscreen	Virtual plane points for infield design	Unique mapping

TUD	Tool movement		
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Table 56: C35 Control function summary table

When a target model is created in relation to local objects (curb, walls, roadside), the operator can use the tip of the bucket to take a measurement of the height of the object of interest. By teaching new points with respect to this height, the operator is able to create virtual planes. This infield-design approach enables the operator to create digital design models by his own. The created designs can be visualized in the main GUI Figure 44.

Figure 45: Projection of the design data on the digital terrain model

6.2.2.6 C36 - Operator adjusts views in terminal display switching between camera and 3D machine and environment views

Summary

Partner	Input device	Controlled values	Mapping(s)
TUD	Touchscreen,	Current active view	Unique mapping
TUD	Physical control panel		

Table 57: C36 Control function summary table

6.2.2.6.1 Touchscreen

With a swipe gesture, the operator is able to switch between several views, including camera and 3D-visualization

6.2.2.6.2 Physical control panel

The same functionality for the switching of views is mapped on a joystick button.

6.2.2.7 C37 - Operator activates collision warning and surface assistance

Summary

Partner	Input device	Controlled values	Mapping(s)
TUD	Touchscreen,	ON/OFF of assistance function	Unique mapping
TUD	Physical control		

Table 58: C37 Control function summary table

6.2.2.7.1 Touchscreen

A dedicated button on the touchscreen is used to switch of the assistance functions (collision warning system and surface assistance)

6.2.2.7.2 Physical control panel

A physical push button is used to switch on/off the assistance functions.

6.2.2.8 C38 - Operator adjusts modality and salience of warning according to his needs or situational conditions in advance to the mission

Summary

Partner	Input device	Controlled values	Mapping(s)
TUD	Touchscreen	Appearance of the visualization features	Unique mapping

Table 59: C38 Control function summary table

The visualization feature properties (especially brightness and color) can be individually modified in a dedicated menu in the main GUI.

6.2.2.9 C310 - Select between single panel display and split screen views & view contents

Summary

Partner	Input device	Controlled values	Mapping(s)
TUD	Touchscreen	Screen layout	Unique mapping

Table 60: C38 Control function summary table

Even though implementing XR interaction technologies such as lightbars, matrix displays and environment projections, terminal displays are needed to provide more complex visualizations and views. As information requirements differ throughout operation activities, operators need to change screen layouts to maximize visibility of situationally important views. This mainly applies to camera and augmented virtual machine views that contain higher levels of information complexity. Through a layout shift function, realized by a button in the terminal-GUI, operators can switch between a set of predefined screen layout that cover split screen and single screen displays of each view.

6.3 Modes of information presentation (feedback)

The analysis of the vision scenarios presented in Section 5.1 above yields the list of individual feedback functions in Table 16 in the appendix Section 8.6 below.

6.3.1 State of the art

The use of small displays is common in excavators. In basic configurations, these are used to show camera streams for environment surveillance (F310) or visualize machine and process data (F31, F32, F33, F311, F312, F313, F314). With the age of advanced digital modelling and connectivity, bigger touch displays were introduced in excavators. They are used to display virtual models of the machine, the construction site and the environment and provide map, communication, maintenance, and task planning functions. Successful machine operation is mainly assessed through direct visual feedback from the concerned machine parts.

6.3.2 Feedback functions prototyped in simulation

This section presents the control functions prototyped in simulation for use-case UC2, following the same approach as that described in the introduction of Section 4.3.2 above.

6.3.2.1 F32 - Inform operator of intended excavation geometry

Summary

Partner	Output device	Displayed values	Mapping(s)
TUD	Projection in simulation	Outline of target design	Unique mapping

Table 61: F32 Feedback function summary table

The target design (e.g. for a pit) is displayed in the virtual scene as a projection to the digital terrain model.

6.3.2.2 F33 - Inform operator of distance to the target excavation depth

Summary

Partner	Output device	Displayed values	Mapping(s)
TUD	Matrix display	height difference between target and actual	Unique mapping
TUD	indicators in the main GUI	height of the tool	

Table 62: F33 Feedback function summary table

6.3.2.2.1 Matrix display

The Matrix display on the bottom of the excavator's arm is used to indicate the height difference between actual position and target height. The matrix display can be visualized virtually in the simulation or as a hardware device. The same information is encoded as colored bars in the main GUI.

Figure 46: Matrix Display in the simulation environment

6.3.2.2.2 Light bars

The main GUI shows the difference to the target height between the right and the left tip of the bucket as side bars in the main GUI.

6.3.2.3 F34 - Provide operator with a digital terrain model of the actual surrounding.

Summary

Partner	Output device	Displayed values	Mapping(s)
TUD	3D Rendering in the main GUI	Digital terrain model (height map)	Unique Mapping

Table 63: F34 Feedback function summary table

The operator is able to scan the surrounding with a lidar that is mounted on the cabin roof. The resulting point cloud is used to create a height map of the surrounding. This creates a reference between the digital machine twin and the digital design data. This is helpful, because the operator can perform a plausibility check, if the design corresponds to the surrounding and that the parameterization of the machine and the especially the tool geometry is correct. The map can also be coloured with respect to the height difference to the design data. This allows a better planning of the distribution of soil, see Figure 47.

Figure 47: Height map visualization with height difference colouring

6.3.2.4 F35 - Inform operator about detected obstacles in the vicinity

Summary

Partner	Output device	Displayed values	Mapping(s)
TUD	Light bars	Direction and risk of a potential collision with a person	Unique mapping

Table 64: F35 Feedback function summary table

With a camera-based person detection system, the left, right and rear of the machine is monitored. If a person is detected, the risk of a collision is assessed and indicated with an LED-stripe around the front facing window. The lower the risk, the smaller and greener the LED lights up in the direction of the object. If the risk increases, the LED turns to red and get bigger, see Figure 48.

Figure 48: LED-Stripe to indicate persons in the surrounding of the machine

6.3.2.5 F36 - Inform operator of an immediate danger in the vicinity

Summary

Partner	Output device	Displayed values	Mapping(s)
TUD	Light bars	Direction and risk of a potential collision with a person	Unique mapping
TUD	Light bars around screen	Direction and risk of a potential collision with a person	Unique mapping
TUD	Markers in top-down view	Direction and risk of a potential collision with a person	Unique mapping

Table 65: F36 Feedback function summary table

6.3.2.5.1 Light bars

The light bars around the front facing window indicate with a big red light, that there is an immediate danger.

6.3.2.5.2 Light bars around terminal display screen

The light bars around the display map the same information as the lights around the window.

6.3.2.5.3 Markers in top-down view

In the top view of the machine, in the main GUI, the detected objects are visualized, see Figure 50.

Figure 49: Feedback modalities to visualize immediate danger of a collision with a person

6.3.2.6 F37 - Inform operator of buried hazard in excavation area

Summary

Partner	Output device	Displayed values	Mapping(s)
TUD	Matrix display	Underground media below the bucket	Unique mapping
TUD	Display on the tablet		

Table 66: F37 Feedback function summary table

6.3.2.6.1 Matrix display

The matrix display shows an additional animation if underground media is closely under the bucket.

6.3.2.6.2 Display on the tablet

The underground media information is visualized in the 3D-scene.

6.3.2.7 F310 - Inform persons around that the object detection system has registered them

Summary

Partner	Output device	Displayed values	Mapping(s)
TUD	Light bars around the outside of the cabin?	Whether the object is detected or not.	Unique mapping

Table 67: F310 Feedback function summary table

It is a valuable information for outstanding people, that they get a confirmation, that the AI-based person detection system recognizes them. With an LED-stripe, this external HMI can indicate the same information as the LED-Stripe in the cabin.

6.3.2.8 F311 - Inform operator that the tool movement is within intended digging area

Summary

Partner	Output device	Displayed values	Mapping(s)
TUD	Touch Screen	encode with dedicated animations, the tool is within the given tolerance	Unique mapping
TUD	Matrix display	encode with dedicated animations, the tool is within the given tolerance	Unique mapping

Table 68: F311 Feedback function summary table

6.3.2.8.1 Touch Screens

The sidebars indicate, that the tool is within the target design by coloring and lighting up arrows on the side bar widgets.

6.3.2.8.2 Matrix display

The matrix display has a fine mode, that indicates the position of the tool within the tolerance as well, whether the movement is going towards the lower or upper limit of the tolerance band. In the coarse mode, the indicators visualize, how far the tool is away from the target design, see Figure 51

Figure 50: LED Matrix-Design for the fine and coarse mode for the height indication

6.3.2.9 F312 - Inform operator about the location of the edges of the trench/pit

Summary

Partner	Output device	Displayed values	Mapping(s)
TUD	Tablet GUI	Design data outline	Unique Mapping

Table 69: F312 Feedback function summary table

The outline of the design data is projected on the surface. The height indicator responds on height differences within the target design. Leaving the target design leads to a disabling of height difference visualization.

7 Conclusions

Building on the previous Deliverable D4.4, the present deliverable D4.8 describes the interaction model used for ideating control and feedback functions for the user interface (UI) in all three THEIA^{XR} use-cases. It then details the technical implementations for each of these functions, whenever they were implemented in some form of simulation. This provides an overview of the simulated interactions developed for each of the use-cases, as well as the extent to which the insights from the co-design process run in task T3.2 “*Scenario-based co-design of interaction concepts*” have been translated into concrete simulation prototypes.

We begin by an analysis of the latest available versions of the use-case scenarios provided in task T3.2 (Deliverables D3.2 and D3.7 “*Interaction Scenarios*”). This analysis is based on an interaction model in which any event in an operation scenario requires either the implementation of a control function, the implementation of a feedback function, or both. Control functions imply that the operator uses a UI element to trigger and control an action executed by the vehicle, tool or UI. Thus, a specific mapping of UI component input values to vehicle, tool or UI setpoints or states must be defined. Similarly, feedback functions require the vehicle’s internal software and sensors to acquire sensor values, process them in a defined manner, and map the resulting values to outputs on a UI component. The feedback mapping must therefore be defined in a similar manner to the way control mappings are defined.

We iteratively refined the set of control and feedback functions, ending up with a short list for each use-case. We then decided whether or not to implement these functions in simulation on a function-by-function basis, reporting the extent of simulation implementation when applicable. This deliverable thereby provides an overview of the algorithmics underlying a majority of the interactions envisioned in THEIA^{XR}. This overview is complemented by a description of the simulation environments designed for each use-case, as well as a short review of the state-of-the-art for interactions with the vehicle UI in each use-case.

These descriptions thus serve as a basis for further integration of novel interactions into the real vehicle user interfaces, as well as for evaluations of interactions performed in simulation, both of which will be the focus of tasks T6.1 “*Integration and use case implementation*” and T6.2 “*Testing and demonstration*”. Tasks and deliverables making use of the simulated implementations of control and feedback functions described herein can subsequently refer to the present deliverable to provide detailed context on the implementations of the functions being integrated and evaluated.

References

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- [3] <https://www.ti.com/lit/ds/symlink/drv2605.pdf?ts=1708437852271> (RETRIEVED: 17/02/2024)

ABBREVIATIONS / ACRONYMS

[3D]	3-Dimensional
[AR]	Augmented Reality
[CAN]	Control Area Network
[COM]	Center Of Mass
[CPU]	Central Processing Unit
[D#.#]	Deliverable #.#
[DoF]	Degree(s) of Freedom
[DTM]	Digital Terrain Model
[ECU]	Electronic Control Unit
[FoV]	Field of View
[GNSS]	Global Navigation Satellite System
[GUI]	Graphical User Interface
[HMI]	Human-Machine Interface
[HW]	Hardware
[IMU]	Inertial Measurement Unit
[IO]	Input/Output
[IPC]	Industrial Personal Computer
[ISO]	International Standards Organization
[KPI]	Key Performance Indicator(s)
[LED]	Light-Emitting Diode
[LiDAR]	Light Detection and Ranging
[M#]	Month #
[N.A.]	Not Applicable
[PC]	Personal Computer
[PID]	Proportional Integral Derivative (Controller)
[RC]	Remote-Controlled
[SAE]	Society of Automotive Engineers
[SW]	Software
[T#.#]	Task #.#
[UC#]	Use-Case #
[UI]	User Interface
[WP#.#]	Work Package #.#
[XR]	eXtended Reality
[YOLO]	You Only Look Once

8 APPENDIX A: VIBROTACTILE FEEDBACK LIBRARY

For the purposes of the vibrotactile feedback functions designed in use-cases UC1 (snow grooming) and UC2 (logistics), Haption developed prototype vibrotactile controllers based on Arduino micro controllers (these are described in more detail in deliverable D5.6 “*Multimodal Immersive Cockpit (final version)*”). The custom-designed firmware and protocol for interfacing with them allows the generation of 23 distinct vibrotactile cues, which can be triggered, stopped, in some cases looped, and assigned to a given actuator at any time.

To allow this, vibrotactile cues are defined as a single byte message (Little endian):

Bits 1-3			Bits 4-8				
0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Actuator Mapping Bits			Cue Bits				

Table 70: Vibrotactile cue triggers structure

Currently, cues are built as fixed patterns defined with a set of frequencies, durations, intensities as a fraction of a pre-defined full intensity, and rates in the event that the cues repeat. Adjusting the cue intensities requires re-flashing the vibrotactile controller with an updated firmware.

8.1 Actuator mapping bits

Actuator Mapping Bits	Actuator Mapping
0b_000	Special: Stop All Cues (ignore the rest of the byte)
0b_010	Trigger cue on track controls right stick
0b_100	Trigger cue on track controls left stick
0b_001	Trigger cue on primary haptic device handle
0b_110	Trigger cue on track controls left & right (in quick sequence)
0b_101	Trigger cue on track controls left stick and on primary device handle
0b_011	Trigger cue on track controls right stick and on primary device handle
0b_111	Trigger cue on all actuators (cues on track controls left and right played in rapid sequence, cue on primary handle played concurrently)

Table 71: Bits mapping vibrotactile cues to actuators

Triggering a cue on a device while another is running on said device has the effect of overriding it (there is no queue for requested cues). Triggering a cue on a device has no effect on concurrent cues that would already be playing on the other device.

8.2 Cue bits

Cue Name	Cue code	Description	Example application scenario
STOP_CUE	0b_0_0000	Stops the cue currently running on the actuator.	n.a.
VIB_250	0b_0_0001	Vibrate at 250Hz (full intensity) for 0.25s	Basic building block for more complex cues, e.g. signal approaching obstacle (UC1)

VIB_120	0b_0_0010	Vibrate at 120Hz (full intensity) for 0.25s	Basic building block for more complex cues
VIB_370	0b_0_0011	Vibrate at 370Hz (full intensity) for 0.25s	Basic building block for more complex cues
CLICK_HF	0b_0_0100	Click high frequency loud	Basic building block for more complex cues
CLICK_LF	0b_0_0101	Click low frequency loud	Basic building block for more complex cues
IMPACT	0b_0_0110	Impact pulse	Inform of container contact with ground or truck (UC2)
LOCK_OPEN	0b_0_0111	Lock opening vibration pattern	Signal that twistlocks have been disengaged (UC2)
LOCK_CLOSE	0b_0_1000	Lock closing vibration pattern	Signal that twistlocks have been engaged (UC2)
PULSE_T1	0b_0_1001	Pulse train (8ms pulse, 100ms period)	Signal approaching target spreader pose (UC2)
PULSE_T2	0b_0_1010	Pulse train (8ms pulse, 200ms period)	
PULSE_T3	0b_0_1011	Pulse train (8ms pulse, 300ms period)	
PULSE_T4	0b_0_1100	Pulse train (8ms pulse, 400ms period)	
PULSE_T5	0b_0_1101	Pulse train (8ms pulse, 500ms period)	
PULSE_T6	0b_0_1110	Pulse train (8ms pulse, 600ms period)	
PULSE_T7	0b_0_1111	Pulse train (8ms pulse, 700ms period)	
PULSE_T8	0b_1_0000	Pulse train (8ms pulse, 800ms period)	
PULSE_T9	0b_1_0001	Pulse train (8ms pulse, 900ms period)	
PULSE_T10	0b_1_0010	Pulse train (8ms pulse, 1s period)	
NOTIF_LOUD	0b_1_0011	Loud “notification pending” vibration pattern	Signal urgent vehicle notification, e.g. oil level getting low
NOTIF_MED	0b_1_0100	Medium intensity “notification pending” vibration pattern	Signal non-urgent vehicle notification, e.g. job system data transmission failure (UC2)
NOTIF_QUIET	0b_1_0101	Quiet “notification pending” vibration pattern	Signal non-critical event, e.g. low windscreen wiper liquid
DANGER_OUT_OF_RANGE_H	0b_1_0110	Loud “out of ideal range (too high)” vibration pattern consisting of loud continuous vibrations ramping down in frequency (280Hz to 80Hz).	Snowgroomer deviating far from lane to the right
OUT_OF_RANGE_H	0b_1_0111	Similar to DANGER_OUT_OF_RANGE_H, however the vibration is interrupted with pauses and ramps down in intensity as it ramps down in frequency, providing less harsh of a cue.	Snowgroomer slightly deviating from lane to the right

DANGER_OUT_OF_RANGE_L	0b_1_1000	Same as DANGER_OUT_OF_RANGE_H, however the frequency ramp is inverted (80Hz to 280Hz).	Snowgroomer deviating far from lane to the left
OUT_OF_RANGE_L	0b_1_1001	Same as OUT_OF_RANGE_H, however the frequency ramp is inverted (80Hz to 280Hz).	Snowgroomer slightly deviating from lane to the left
OUT_OF_LANE	0b_1_1010	« Out of lane » rattle: Light 50Hz rattle on the left or right track control similar to driving over road lane limits. The vibration occurs with a period of 1s, i.e. 0.5s of rattling followed by 0.5s of silence	Signal snowgroomer overshooting target lane (UC1)
WARNING_UNSAFE	0b_1_1011	Warning “unsafe”: Alternating 0.15s vibrations at full intensity, switching between 160Hz and 100Hz	Signal dangerous machine state
MENU_SELECT	0b_1_1100	Menu element selection button click: Two soft short pulses separated by a 10ms pause	n.a.
MENU_CHANGE	0b_1_1101	Menu element change click: Soft short pulse	n.a.
ENDSTOP	0b_1_1110	Endstop impact: Soft short impact pulse	UC1 Snowgroomer blade or UC2 boom/spreader axis driven to endstop
FAILURE	0b_1_1111	Warning of failure: Sequence of a 0.2s high-frequency (280Hz) and a 0.1s low-frequency (100Hz) vibration	Signal failure to execute a desired action (e.g. twistlock locking when not available in UC2)

Table 72: Vibrotactile cue library